

Bachelor Thesis

pyMOR QR decomposition performance analysis and development of heuristics

Revised version

Maximilian Bindhak

August 14, 2024

First Reviewer:
Prof. Dr. Michael Kuhn

Second Reviewer:
Dr. Jens Saak

Abstract

The state-of-the-art QR decomposition in pyMOR, a repeated Modified Gram-Schmidt, is numerically robust at the cost of long runtimes. Potentially faster and more efficient algorithms from different papers are implemented in pyMOR. They are quantified, using a self implemented proof of concept benchmarking tool. A new shifted Cholesky QR variant is found, which seems to be numerically stable. It performs the best in many cases. Furthermore, norm estimation variants are analyzed, to further improve the runtime of the Shifted Cholesky QR for large Gramian matrices. The QR decomposition CGS IRO LS turns out to be even faster in some use cases compared to the shifted Cholesky QR. These cases include orthogonalizing a few vectors against an orthonormal basis or just a few vectors in general. Performance monitoring was conducted on the algorithms to observe their efficiency and to find potential bottlenecks.

Contents

1. Introduction	1
2. Linear Algebra and Numerical Mathematics	2
2.1. Inner product	2
2.2. Orthogonal and orthonormal basis	2
2.3. Singular Values and Singular Value Decomposition	3
2.4. Norms	3
2.4.1. Vector Norm	3
2.4.2. Matrix Norm	4
2.5. Matrix Condition Number	5
2.6. QR decomposition	6
2.7. Errors	7
2.7.1. Relative error	7
2.8. Stability	9
3. QR decomposition	10
3.1. Gram-Schmidt QR decomposition	10
3.1.1. Classical Gram-Schmidt	10
3.1.2. CGS IRO LS	11
3.1.3. CGS P IRO	12
3.1.4. MGS	12
3.2. Cholesky QR	13
3.2.1. SCQR	14
3.3. Householder-QR	14
4. Benchmark Setup	15
4.1. Test Matrix	15
4.2. Software installation, System and miscellaneous Options	16
4.3. Benchmarking prototype	18
4.4. Overview and outline of used plot/graph types	22
5. Shifted Cholesky QR decomposition implementation and benchmarks	24
5.1. Shift Strategies	24
5.1.1. Over matrix condition number	25
5.1.2. Over matrix size-ratio	27
5.1.3. Surface plot	27
5.2. Recalculated shift values in iterations	28
5.3. SCQR norm calculation	29
5.3.1. Eigenvalue solvers	30
5.3.2. Frobenius norm	31
5.3.3. Over matrix size-ratio	32
5.3.4. Over matrix condition number	34
5.3.5. Surface plot	34
5.4. Shifted Cholesky QR with non-euclidian inner product	38

6. QR decomposition benchmarks	40
6.1. Over matrix condition number	40
6.2. Over Matrix size-ratio	41
6.3. Surface plot	41
6.4. Over Columns to Orthogonalize	42
7. Performance monitoring	49
7.1. LIKWID	49
7.2. Over Matrix Condition Number	51
7.3. Over Matrix Size-Ratio	52
8. Summary, Conclusions and Future Plans	55
A. System Specifications	59
B. Matrix size-ratio table	61
C. Additional Performance Monitoring Plots	62

List of Figures

2.1.	In this graphic $M = A$ and $V^* = V^T$. In the illustration the unit disk (light blue) together with the two unit vectors (magenta and yellow) are transformed by the matrix M . The transformation is split into 2 rotations by V^* and U and a scaling by the singular values in Σ which stretch the unit disk along the x and y axes (dark blue) by some value. Image by [11].	4
3.1.	Classical Gram-Schmidt visualization	11
a.	11
b.	11
c.	11
d.	11
e.	11
5.1.	Comparison between recalculated and fixed shift SCQR variant. Both variants use eigsh with a tolerance of 10^{-4} to estimate the norm of the Gramian. Over matrix condition number plot for $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ with $n = 10^4$ generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.	25
5.2.	Comparison between recalculated and fixed shift SCQR variant. Both variants use eigsh with a tolerance of 10^{-4} to estimate the norm of the Gramian. Over matrix size-ratio plot for $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$ generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.	26
5.3.	Comparison between recalculated and fixed shift SCQR variant. Both variants use eigsh with a tolerance of 10^{-4} to estimate the norm of the Gramian. For the variants the runtime and error metrics are visualized. Surface plot with varying matrix size-ratio on the x-axis and matrix condition number on the y-axis generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.	27
5.4.	Comparison between SCQR variants with different norm estimation algorithms. Over matrix size-ratio plot for $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$ generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.	33
5.5.	Comparison between SCQR variants with different norm estimation algorithms. Over matrix condition number plot for $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ with $n = 10^4$ generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.	35
5.6.	Comparison 1/2 between SCQR variants with different norm estimation algorithms. For every variant the runtime and error metrics are visualized. Surface plot with varying matrix size-ratio on the x-axis and matrix condition number on the y-axis generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.	36
5.7.	Comparison 2/2 between SCQR variants with different norm estimation algorithms. For every variant the runtime and error metrics are visualized. Surface plot with varying matrix size-ratio on the x-axis and matrix condition number on the y-axis generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.	37
5.8.	Comparison between a few selected SCQR variants with different norm estimation algorithms. For the variants just the relative Speedup is plotted. Surface plot with varying matrix size-ratio on the x-axis and matrix condition number on the y-axis generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.	37

6.1.	Comparison between QR variants. Over matrix condition number plot for $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ with $n = 10^4$ generated with seeds $\{0, 1, \dots, 4\}$ with 1 iteration each.	44
6.2.	Comparison between QR variants. Over matrix size-ratio plot for $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$ generated with seeds $\{0, 1, \dots, 4\}$ with 1 iteration each.	45
6.3.	Comparison between QR variants. For every variant the runtime and error metrics are visualized. Surface plot with varying matrix size-ratio on the x-axis and matrix condition number on the y-axis generated with seeds $\{0, 1 \dots, 4\}$ with 1 iteration each.	46
6.4.	Comparison between a few selected QR decomposition variants. For the variants just the relative Speedup is plotted. Surface plot with varying matrix size-ratio on the x-axis and matrix condition number on the y-axis generated with seeds $\{0, 1 \dots, 4\}$ with 1 iteration each.	47
6.5.	Comparison between QR variants. Just the runtime is plotted along the y-axis. Plots for matrices with size-ratios $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \in \{0, 2, 4\}$ and condition number $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{7.5}$ generated with seeds $\{0, 1 \dots, 4\}$ with 1 iterations each. Along the x-axis the number of columns orthogonalized against an already existing orthonormal basis is specified.	48
7.1.	LIKWID performance monitoring plots. Comparison between QR variants. Over matrix condition number plot for $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ with $n = 10^4$ generated with seed 0 with 1 iteration each.	53
7.2.	LIKWID performance monitoring plots. Comparison between QR variants. Over matrix size-ratio plot for $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$ generated with seed 0 with 1 iteration each.	54
A.1.	System topology generated using 1stopo.	60
C.1.	LIKWID performance monitoring plots. Comparison between QR variants. Over matrix condition number plot for $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ with $n = 10^4$ generated with seed 0 with 2 iterations each.	63
C.2.	LIKWID performance monitoring plots. Comparison between QR variants. Over matrix size-ratio plot for $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$ generated with seed 0 with 2 iterations each.	64

Chapter 1.

Introduction

The QR decomposition is one of the most fundamental concepts of linear algebra. It is widely used in model order reduction (MOR) methods, including proper orthogonal decomposition, balanced truncation, and moment-matching methods. These methods all rely on numerically stable decompositions. In pyMOR¹, an open source python library implementing a variety of model order reduction algorithms, the state-of-the-art QR decomposition is a repeated modified Gram-Schmidt. This variant is numerically robust at the cost of long runtimes.

Matrices resulting from snapshot or sampling based discretizations can become huge and are often ‘tall’ and ‘skinny’.

Potentially faster and more efficient algorithms are implemented and tested. pyMOR uses the so-called VectorArray interface, to abstract matrices. This allows seamless integration of different backends and PDE solvers, like NumPy, FEniCS and NGSolve. Furthermore, it simplifies the implementation of algorithms for MPI distribution. Because of this, the access onto a matrix is restricted to vectors only. All algorithms implemented in pyMOR have to use this interface. This limits the options of usable QR decompositions.

One promising variant is the novel shifted Cholesky QR (SCQR), which was introduced in [10] and is based on the Cholesky QR (CQR). As the name implies, a shift is used, which can be expensive to compute in some cases. Furthermore, the proposed Algorithms 4.1 and 4.2 are unstable. It is compared against a new variant, in which the shift is recalculated in every iteration. The paper [7], and the accompanying GitHub repository [18]², provide a great overview of Gram-Schmidt based decompositions, of which, two are also included. Furthermore, the highly efficient Householder QR implementations from LAPACK, accessed through the NumPy and SciPy functions, are used as a baseline.

The performance and numerical stability are quantified by use of a proof of concept tool, developed for this thesis, which is designed to simplify parameter rich benchmarking. Additionally, performance monitoring results, that are measured using LIKWID, are shown. This gives further insights into how efficient the algorithms are, and also how much they utilize the given hardware.

¹For further reading into pyMOR, refer to [20].

The pyMOR GitHub repository can be found at <https://github.com/pymor/pymor>.

²The repository is also based on their other work, which can be found in [8, 21, 22].

Chapter 2.

Linear Algebra and Numerical Mathematics

This chapter serves as a short summary on the linear algebra and numerics needed for this thesis. Further in-depth explanations can be found in [12] and [24]. In the following, some definitions have been adapted, since the focus of this thesis lies on real vector spaces.

2.1. Inner product

The inner product $\langle x, y \rangle_B$ of two vectors $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is defined by

$$\langle x, y \rangle_B = x^\top B y \quad (2.1)$$

for a matrix $B \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, which has to be symmetric positive-definite¹. It allows for definitions like length of a vector, angles between two vectors and orthogonality, by projecting one vector onto the other. An inner product has to fulfil the following properties:

1. Positive-definiteness $\langle x, x \rangle_B \geq 0$ and $x = 0 \Leftrightarrow \langle x, x \rangle_B = 0$ (2.2)

2. Symmetry $\langle x, y \rangle_B = \langle y, x \rangle_B$ (2.3)

3. Linearity $\langle \alpha x + \beta y, z \rangle_B = \alpha \langle x, z \rangle_B + \beta \langle y, z \rangle_B$ (2.4)

The best known inner product is the Euclidean product, which is also referred to as scalar or dot product. For this product the matrix B is the unit matrix $B = I$, and the Equation (2.1) can be simplified to

$$\begin{aligned} \langle x, y \rangle_B &= \langle x, y \rangle \\ &= x^\top y \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^m x_i y_i \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

Unless otherwise mentioned the Euclidean inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ will be used. All definitions and algorithms can be derived for non-Euclidean inner product spaces as well.

2.2. Orthogonal and orthonormal basis

Two vectors v, w are considered orthogonal according to a scalar product, if $\langle v, w \rangle_B = 0$. The columns of a matrix $V = [v_1, \dots, v_n]$ form an orthogonal basis², if all v_i, v_j are orthogonal for

¹pp. 160-161 in [12]

²pp. 37-38 in [24]

$1 \leq i < j \leq n$. Furthermore, an orthogonal basis is orthonormal, if all vectors v_i are of length 1, i.e. $\langle v_i, v_i \rangle_B = 1$. A matrix with orthonormal columns is called orthogonal. The inverse of an orthogonal, square matrix Q is equal to Q transposed.

$$Q^T = Q^{-1} \quad (2.6)$$

2.3. Singular Values and Singular Value Decomposition

The Singular Value Decomposition (SVD)³ is the decomposition of a matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ into 3 matrices $A = U\Sigma V^T$. In this thesis I will use the definition of economy size SVD given by $U \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times r}$, $\Sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$ and $V^T \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times n}$ with $r = \text{rank}(A)$. Both U and V are orthogonal matrices and

$$\Sigma = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 & & & \\ & \ddots & & \\ & & \sigma_r & \\ & & & \end{bmatrix}$$

is a diagonal matrix containing the so-called singular values $\sigma_i \in \mathbb{R}$ and $0 < \sigma_r \leq \dots \leq \sigma_1$, which indicate the stretch along each axis. Furthermore, let $\sigma_{\max}(A) = \sigma_1$. A matrix is called singular, if it is rank deficient, i.e. $r < \min m, n$.

2.4. Norms

A norm⁴ is a function $\|\cdot\| : \mathbb{R}^n \mapsto \mathbb{R}$, which has to fulfill the following properties

$$1. \text{ Positive Definiteness} \quad \|x\| \geq 0 \quad x = 0 \Leftrightarrow \|x\| = 0 \quad (2.7)$$

$$2. \text{ Linearity} \quad \|\alpha x\| = |\alpha| \|x\| \quad (2.8)$$

$$3. \text{ Triangular inequality} \quad \|x + y\| \leq \|x\| + \|y\| \quad (2.9)$$

Two norms A, B are considered equivalent, if there exists $c, C \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$, such that

$$c\|x\|_A \leq \|x\|_B \leq C\|x\|_A \quad (2.10)$$

2.4.1. Vector Norm

Every inner product induces a vector norm

$$\|x\| = \sqrt{\langle x, x \rangle_B} \quad (2.11)$$

³pp. 76-77 in [12]

⁴pp. 68-70 in [12]

$$M = U \cdot \Sigma \cdot V^*$$

Figure 2.1.: In this graphic $M = A$ and $V^* = V^T$. In the illustration the unit disk (light blue) together with the two unit vectors (magenta and yellow) are transformed by the matrix M . The transformation is split into 2 rotations by V^* and U and a scaling by the singular values in Σ which stretch the unit disk along the x and y axes (dark blue) by some value. Image by [11].

Another group of important vector norms are the p-norms defined by

$$\|x\|_p = \left(\sum_{i=1}^m |x_i|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \quad (2.12)$$

Well known p-norms are the Manhattan norm, Euclidean norm and maximum norm with $p = 1, 2, \infty$ respectively.

2.4.2. Matrix Norm

Norms on matrices, defined by $\|\cdot\| : \mathbb{R}^{m \times n} \mapsto \mathbb{R}$, are called matrix norms⁵. Essential matrix norms are the so-called vector norms induced matrix norm defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \|A\| &= \sup_{x \neq 0} \frac{\|Ax\|}{\|x\|} \\ &= \sup_{\|x\|=1} \|Ax\| \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

⁵pp. 71-73 in [12]

for a vector norm $\|\cdot\|$. Additionally, it satisfies the following 2 properties

$$4. \text{ Sub-multiplicativity} \quad \|AB\| \leq \|A\| \cdot \|B\| \quad (2.14)$$

$$5. \text{ Compatible with vector norm} \quad \|Ax\| \leq \|A\| \cdot \|x\| \quad (2.15)$$

Furthermore, the norm of orthogonal matrix is always 1, if the norm is induced by a vector norm.

$$\|Q\| = 1 \quad (2.16)$$

Throughout this thesis, the matrix 2-norm, which is also called spectral norm, will be used. It is induced by the vector 2-norm and further defined as

$$\|A\|_2 = \sqrt{\lambda_{\max}(A^T A)} \quad (2.17)$$

$$= \sigma_{\max}(A) \quad (2.18)$$

The equality in Equation (2.18) can be seen when looking at the SVD of A . This definition is intuitive, because it is defined as the largest scaling of this matrix in any direction. Computing the largest singular value can be expensive. However, symmetric matrices, like $A^T A$, can be solved significantly faster using symmetric eigenvalue solvers compared to regular eigenvalue solvers or an *SVD*.

The Frobenius norm is another important norm in numerics.

$$\|A\|_F = \left(\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij}^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.19)$$

It is simple to calculate, and the solution involves every entry of a matrix directly. This makes it useful for evaluating overall errors in matrices. It is however numerically unstable⁶ and not induced by a vector norm⁷.

The following norm equivalence exists between the Frobenius norm and 2-norm⁸

$$\|A\|_2 \leq \|A\|_F \leq \sqrt{\min\{m, n\}} \|A\|_2 \quad (2.20)$$

which will be used in Section 5.1.

2.5. Matrix Condition Number

The condition number is one of the fundamental definitions of numerics. It is a relative measure of how an error scales for an operation, or heuristically speaking, how sensitive the function is to minor changes in the argument. Let κ_2 be the 2-norm based matrix condition number⁹. If

⁶See Section 2.8

⁷Equation (2.15) does apply to the Frobenius norm.

⁸pg. 72 in [12]

⁹pp. 88 in [12]

the matrix A is singular the condition number will have the value $\kappa_2(A) = \infty$, otherwise it is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}\kappa_2(A) &= \|A\|_2 \cdot \|A^{-1}\|_2 \\ &= \frac{\sigma_{\max}(A)}{\sigma_{\min}(A)}\end{aligned}\tag{2.21}$$

The values of an inverse diagonal matrix are just the reciprocal values of the diagonal matrix itself. Therefore, the smallest singular value of A , is the largest of A^{-1} (See Equation (2.22)).

$$\begin{aligned}\|A^{-1}\|_2 &= \|V\Sigma^{-1}U^T\|_2 \\ &= \sigma_{\max}(\Sigma^{-1})\end{aligned}\tag{2.22}$$

Orthogonal matrices have a condition number of 1. Which means, that they do not introduce numerical errors, when applying orthogonal matrices onto matrices or vectors.

$$\kappa_2(Q) = 1\tag{2.23}$$

For square matrices the matrix condition number can also be defined using eigenvalues. This will be further looked at in Chapter 5.

Since the 2-norm is directly connected to singular values, it is easier to create ill conditioned matrices for testing by usage of the SVD, which will be used in Section 4.1. This is the main reason why the 2-norm is used.

2.6. QR decomposition

The QR decomposition¹⁰ of a matrix A is represented by

$$A = QR$$

with Q being an orthogonal matrix, spanning the same vector space as A . This is often referred to as

$$\text{span}(A) = \text{span}(Q)$$

R is an upper triangular matrix.

There are many possible shapes for the matrices Q and R . In this thesis I will mainly focus on the reduced QR decomposition of $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ with $m \geq n$ and $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ and $R \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$. In some cases the result of the QR factorization will have the shapes $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times r}$ and $R \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times n}$, with $r \leq n$. This can happen if A has linearly dependent vectors. Those vectors and the corresponding rows in R are unnecessary and can be removed. For reference, the full decomposition has the shapes $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ and $R \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, where underneath the n -th row of R all values are zero.

¹⁰pp. 246-248 in [12]

2.7. Errors

Due to computer arithmetic, numbers can only be represented with finite precision. In this thesis the data type double was used to represent numbers according to the IEEE-754 Standard¹¹ for Floating-Point Arithmetic. For the numerics, the definition of machine epsilon ε ¹² is highly important. It describes the smallest floating point number, so that $1 + \varepsilon$ is greater than 1, even after rounding. For doubles this value is $2^{-52} \approx 2.22 \cdot 10^{-16}$.

A double has 64 bits, of which the first represents the sign S . After this, there are 11 bits for the exponent E and 52 bits for the Mantissa M , which is also called Fraction. The Mantissa has an implicitly stored 53rd bit, which is always set. A floating point number is defined by

$$(-1)^{(S)_2} \cdot (1.M)_2 \cdot 2^{(E)_2 - 1023}$$

with $(1.M)_2$ meaning, that the bits of the Mantissa are the fractional part of a number. In order to perform an operation between two doubles, the exponents have to match. While adjusting the smaller exponent upwards, the decimal point in $(1.M)_2$ gets shifted to the left. Since there are only 52 bits in the Mantissa, once the number has to be shifted at least 53 times, it becomes de facto zero. If the smaller number has an absolute difference of more than 2^{52} to the larger one, it is practically zero. There are some concepts that try to mitigate this problem, like extended precision formats or software implemented solutions¹³.

Another frequently used value in numerics is the unit roundoff \mathbf{u} , which is the maximum relative error occurring due to rounding. It strongly depends on the rounding method used. For the method "rounding half to even" it is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u} &= \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \\ &\approx 1.11 \cdot 10^{-16} \end{aligned} \tag{2.24}$$

It can best be understood when trying to round the number between 1 and $1 + \varepsilon$ to the next representable number.

Because of this, rules like associativity and distributivity do not apply to computer arithmetic and the order of operations is of utmost significance¹⁴. Special algorithms have to be developed to achieve precise approximations of solutions. This is especially true in linear algebra, since for large matrices small rounding errors can propagate, resulting in even larger errors.

2.7.1. Relative error

In order to analyze and compare the errors of our QR decomposition algorithms I will use the relative error defined by

$$\delta_{\text{err}}(X, \tilde{X}) = \frac{\|\tilde{X} - X\|}{\|X\|} \tag{2.25}$$

¹¹More information about IEEE-754 can be found at [27].

¹²For a more detailed explanation of machine epsilon, refer to [28].

¹³For more information about errors see pp. 93-95 in [12].

¹⁴pg. 29 in [24]

for the exact solution X and the approximation \tilde{X} . This will be used to derive the following three numerical metrics. For the norm the choice fell onto the spectral norm, because of the previously mentioned advantages of matrix norms induced by vector norms. Moreover, the 2-norm is also used for the definition of the matrix condition number.

Loss of Orthogonality

Since Q should be orthogonal after the QR decomposition, $Q^T = Q^{-1}$ should be true and therefore $Q^T Q = I$. The loss of orthogonality will be defined by

$$\delta_{\text{err}}(I, Q^T Q) = \frac{\|Q^T Q - I\|_2}{\|I\|_2} \quad (2.26)$$

$$= \|Q^T Q - I\|_2 \quad (2.27)$$

Relative Cholesky Residual

The Relative Cholesky Residual, given by

$$\delta_{\text{err}}(A^T A, R^T R) = \frac{\|A^T A - R^T R\|_2}{\|A\|_2^2} \quad (2.28)$$

allows one to look at the error in R . The idea behind it is

$$x = A^T A \quad (2.29)$$

$$\approx (QR)^T QR \quad (2.30)$$

$$= R^T Q^T QR \quad (2.31)$$

$$\approx R^T R \quad (2.32)$$

$$= \tilde{x} \quad (2.33)$$

The name and definition of this metric were adapted from [7].

Relative Reconstruction Residual

With both previous metrics one is able to look into the errors in Q and R separately. With the relative reconstruction residual, which is defined as

$$\delta_{\text{err}}(A, QR) = \frac{\|A - QR\|_2}{\|A\|_2} \quad (2.34)$$

one can analyze, how good Q and R ‘match’.

Subspace Angle

Lastly, the Subspace Angle, which is calculated in this thesis using

```
np.max(scipy.linalg.subspace_angle(A, Q))
```

which is also equivalent to

```
scipy.linalg.subspace_angle(A, Q)[0]
```

will be looked at. The SciPy implementation is based on [16]. Reading further into it is recommended. It indicates the largest angle between the two subspaces spanned by the two matrices A and Q . For MOR it is important, that both matrices cover the same subspace. However, one will be able to see, that due to numerics, the algorithms and the shape of the matrices this angle can become quite high.

2.8. Stability

An algorithm is stable, if the error between the exact solution and the approximation is proportional to \mathbf{u} , instead of κ . Many algorithms shown in this thesis will not be stable. Some of them will fail for $\kappa_2(A) \approx \frac{1}{\varepsilon}$ or $\kappa_2(A) \approx \frac{1}{\sqrt{\varepsilon}}$, because they cannot handle the rounding errors well, or will produce errors directly proportional to κ .

Chapter 3.

QR decomposition

In this chapter the QR decomposition algorithms used throughout this thesis are introduced. A great overview of different algorithm variants can be seen in [7]. The paper is accompanied by the GitHub repository [18], which contains a variety of QR implementations in MATLAB. The implementations for CGS, CGS IRO LS and CGS P IRO were modified for usage in pyMOR.

pyMOR supports many matrix backends, all of which have to implement the abstract `VectorArray` interface. In this thesis the `NumpyVectorArray` was used, a wrapper for NumPy `ndarray`'s.

For this chapter it is important to know, that NumPy uses BLAS¹ and LAPACK for linear algebra operations. Both of them are highly optimized and efficient. Often they utilize block technics to subdivide a problem and split it onto multiple threads. BLAS has three so-called levels for Vector-Vector, Matrix-Vector and Matrix-Matrix operations. In particular, the Matrix-Matrix operations (Level 3), like `gemm`, are widely used, since they are by far the most computing-intensive, but at the same time optimized, operations.

3.1. Gram-Schmidt QR decomposition

3.1.1. Classical Gram-Schmidt

The Classical Gram-Schmidt² is a simple QR decomposition based on projection. It is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} A &= [a_1, \dots, a_n] & Q &= [q_1, \dots, q_n] \\ q_1 &= \frac{a_1}{\|a_1\|} \\ \tilde{q}_i &= a_i - \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \langle q_j, a_i \rangle q_j \\ q_i &= \frac{\tilde{q}_i}{\|\tilde{q}_i\|} \\ R_{ii} &= \begin{cases} \|a_1\| & i = 1 \\ \|\tilde{q}_i\| & 1 < i \leq n \end{cases} \\ R_{ji} &= \langle q_j, a_i \rangle \end{aligned}$$

for an inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ and $\forall 1 \leq j < i \leq n$.

¹For the measurements in this thesis OpenBLAS was used.

²p. 254 in [12]

Figure 3.1.: Classical Gram-Schmidt visualization

This can better be understood when looking at the 3D example in Figure 3.1. In Figure 3.1a the red and green vectors are already orthonormalized. The next step is to now project the blue vector onto the existing basis (red and green vectors). The result of the projection can be seen in Figure 3.1b, as the black vectors. This projection can be done using BLAS 2 routines, since the inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ of the vectors of the current orthonormal basis

$$Q_{i-1} = [q_1, \dots, q_{i-1}]$$

with $i = 2, \dots, n$ and the blue vector a_i can be calculated using

$$Q_{i-1}^T \cdot a_i = \begin{bmatrix} \langle q_1, a_i \rangle \\ \vdots \\ \langle q_{i-1}, a_i \rangle \end{bmatrix}$$

The blue vector now has to get subtracted by the linear dependent parts of the already existing basis in Figure 3.1c, in order to make it orthogonal to the basis. The last step is to normalize the blue vector, which can be seen in Figure 3.1d, with the final orthonormal result in Figure 3.1e.

CGS is known to be unstable, as the experiments in Chapter 6 will show. Typically, it has a high loss of orthogonality.

3.1.2. CGS IRO LS

One way to mitigate the loss of orthogonality is a so-called reorthogonalization step. For example the Classical Gram-Schmidt with reorthogonalization (CGS2 or repeated CGS), orthogonalizes each vector twice against the orthonormal basis in every iteration.

The variant CGS IRO LS is a CGS2 variant. It can be found in [26]. However, the operations are rearranged in order to make the algorithm low-synchronous (LS), which should in particular increase performance on distributed systems. However, it strongly depends on how the vectors

and basis are distributed. This is done by orthogonalizing a vector in two iterations instead of twice in one iteration. The orthogonalization steps overlap, i.e. in the second iteration vector 2 and vector 1 get orthogonalized. On MPI distributed systems the norm calculation involves a reduce. Instead of two smaller communication blocks, it now only has one larger block per iteration.

3.1.3. CGS P IRO

Another CGS2 variant is CGS P IRO, which is based on Classical Gram-Schmidt Pythagorean (CGS P), published in [25]. Calculating the norm of \tilde{q}_i causes numerical errors, in particular, if the length of the projected vector is small. Instead, CGS P and CGS P IRO calculate the norm of the vector using the Pythagorean theorem, since the projection onto the basis is orthogonal to the vector \tilde{q}_i , where the length of the Hypotenuse is given by $\|a_i\|$. Equation (3.1) is explicitly formulated to further mitigate numerical errors.

$$\begin{aligned}\|\tilde{q}_i\| &= \sqrt{\|a_i\|^2 - \|Q_{i-1}^T \cdot a_i\|^2} \\ &= \sqrt{\|a_i\| - \|Q_{i-1}^T \cdot a_i\|} \cdot \sqrt{\|a_i\| + \|Q_{i-1}^T \cdot a_i\|}\end{aligned}\quad (3.1)$$

3.1.4. MGS

Due to the order of operations in Figures 3.1b and 3.1c, numerical errors propagate when summing up the projections. However, similar to the Horner scheme for evaluating polynomials, it is possible to rearrange the operations to an equivalent form to CGS that results in a numerically more stable variant. The Modified Gram-Schmidt³ (MGS) is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{q}_i^{(0)} &= a_i \\ \tilde{q}_i^{(j)} &= \tilde{q}_i^{(j-1)} - \langle \tilde{q}_i^{(j-1)}, q_j \rangle q_j \\ q_i &= \frac{\tilde{q}_i^{(i-1)}}{\|\tilde{q}_i^{(i-1)}\|} \\ R_{ii} &= \begin{cases} \|a_1\| & i = 1 \\ \|\tilde{q}_i^{(i-1)}\| & 1 < i \leq n \end{cases} \\ R_{ji} &= \langle \tilde{q}_j^{(j-1)}, q_i \rangle\end{aligned}$$

for all $1 \leq j < i \leq n$. It projects the vector just against one vector from the basis and subtracts the linear dependent components. It repeats this with all vectors from the basis, effectively reducing the algorithm to just vector-vector operations (BLAS 1). This makes it scale worse compared to the other variants, since the projection and subtraction has to be done sequentially.

In pyMOR a Repeated MGS is implemented, which in the following will be referred to as pyMOR Gram-Schmidt (PGS). The vectorized PGS (PGS V) variant is an attempt, to improve

³pp. 254-255 in [12]

the performance of PGS. It removes all linear dependent parts of the upcoming vectors after the repeated orthogonalization step.

3.2. Cholesky QR

Another QR decomposition type is the Cholesky QR (CQR). In order to create Q and R it uses the following algebraic trick

$$\begin{aligned}\text{chol}(A^T A) &= \text{chol}(R^T Q^T Q R) \\ &= \text{chol}(R^T R) \\ &= R\end{aligned}\tag{3.2}$$

$$AR^{-1} = Q\tag{3.3}$$

The first step is to create a Gramian matrix $A^T A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, which is symmetric and positive-definite, if A is non-singular⁴. This Gramian is equal to $R^T R$ in exact arithmetic. Using the Cholesky decomposition, here denoted with $\text{chol}(\cdot)$, one can easily compute the R in Equation (3.2). The last step Equation (3.3) would be to compute Q by evaluating $Q = AR^{-1}$. Important to note for the pyMOR context is that the Gramian $A^T A$ is stored in a `numpy.ndarray`. For small n it is possible to calculate the Cholesky decomposition and inverse effectively on a single machine using BLAS and LAPACK implementations. Therefore, on MPI distributed systems, the Gramian is evaluated and stored on rank 0.

However, the CQR has a huge drawback. As seen in Equation (3.4) the matrix condition number of the Gramian is the square of the condition number of the input matrix.

$$\begin{aligned}\kappa_2(A^T A) &= \kappa_2(V \Sigma^T U^T U \Sigma V^T) \\ &= \kappa_2(V \Sigma^2 V^T) \\ &= \kappa_2(\Sigma^2) \\ &= \sigma_{\max}(\Sigma^2) \cdot \sigma_{\min}(\Sigma^2) \\ &= \sigma_{\max}(A)^2 \cdot \sigma_{\min}(A)^2 \\ &= \kappa_2(A)^2\end{aligned}\tag{3.4}$$

Similar to the CGS2, the Cholesky QR can be applied again in order to reorthogonalize the solution, which is also called CQR2. In further iterations the Gramian has to be recalculated using $Q^T Q$. This only works up to a condition number of around $\kappa_2(A) \approx \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mathbf{u}}}$. With even higher matrix condition numbers the Cholesky decomposition starts to fail, due to accumulation of numerical errors. Typically, this also happens if the matrix is not positive-definite, but instead semi positive-definite, with at least one eigenvalue, and therefore singular value, being zero. For high condition numbers at least one eigenvalue is too small and possibly due to arithmetic considered to be zero.

⁴If A is singular the Gramian is semi positive-definite.

3.2.1. SCQR

Paper [10] introduced and proved new algorithms based on CQR2. In Algorithm 4.1, if the Cholesky decomposition breaks down, the shift (see Equation (3.5)) is evaluated and applied onto the diagonal of the Gramian. If the matrix fulfills $\kappa_2(A) \leq \frac{\mathbf{u}^{-1}}{96(mn+n(n+1))}$, 3 iterations of CQR guarantee a good approximation. The Equation (3.5) for the shift s supposedly calculates a value large enough, to not let the Cholesky decomposition fail, but also small enough to not introduce large errors. This results in an increase of the smallest eigenvalue by magnitudes, while it minimally affects the largest eigenvalue.

$$R = \text{chol}(A^T A + s \cdot I)$$

$$s = \begin{cases} 11(mn + n(n + 1))\mathbf{u}\|A\|_2^2 & B = I \\ 11(2m\sqrt{mn} + n(n + 1))\mathbf{u}\|A\|_2^2\|B\|_2 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (3.5)$$

Algorithm 4.2 is based on 4.1. It iterates until a threshold for a residual is reached. After every failed Cholesky decomposition the same shift is applied. The variant 5.1 on the other hand is derived to be compatible for non-euclidian inner products. It is not considered in this thesis.

3.3. Householder-QR

Another QR decomposition is the Householder-QR⁵. It relies on reflections unlike Gram-Schmidt based algorithms using projections. These so-called Householder-Reflectors are orthogonal matrices, which are perfectly conditioned. Efficient implementations, like `*geqrf` from LAPACK, furthermore use Block technics to better partition the problem and utilize BLAS 3 subroutine calls⁶. Both NumPy and SciPy use `*geqrf` (and `*gqr` to construct Q) from LAPACK and will be used for the tests in Chapter 6.

Furthermore, `scipy.linalg.qr_insert`⁷ is being used in Section 6.4. The implementation uses Householder QR to orthogonalize columns, that are added to an orthonormal basis. This will be explained in more detail in Section 6.4. In case, the columns are inserted between the vectors of the basis, Givens Rotation⁸ is used, to fully orthogonalize the matrix.

⁵pp. 234-237, 248-250 in [12]

⁶More about Block Householder QR can be found on pp. 250-251 in [12].

⁷Details about the implementation can be found at https://github.com/scipy/scipy/blob/maintenance/1.10.x/scipy/linalg/_decomp_update.pyx.in#L1880-L2032.

⁸For more information about Givens Rotation, refer to pp. 109-112 in [24].

Chapter 4.

Benchmark Setup

In this chapter the construction of the test matrix is explained. Furthermore, I will present a proof of concept tool, which I developed to simplify the benchmarking process. Lastly I will give a brief introduction to the plot types, that are used throughout this thesis. The collected data and the used code can be found in [6] and [5] respectively. The code consists of a modified version of pyMOR, the used benchmarking files and the developed tool, introduced in Section 4.3.

4.1. Test Matrix

Testing the algorithms requires an input matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$. In [7] a variety of matrices with special structures are used to bring the presented QR algorithms to their limits. In particular the relative Cholesky residual and loss of orthogonality are observed. The chosen construction algorithm for test matrices for this thesis is most similar to the test matrix ‘stewart’, which is being used in [7], since it is also constructing the matrix based on an SVD. The key difference is, that ‘stewart’ adds rank deficiency.

Requirements for the construction algorithm are the following. First, it creates a matrix of size $m \times n$, since tall and skinny matrices are of larger interest. Second, it should be pseudo-randomly generated using a seed s , so that it is both reproducible, but also has an unpredictable structure. A seed can be used to initialize a random number generator, which is done in this case using `numpy.random.seed(s)` to initialize NumPy’s default random number generator. The function `numpy.random.rand` creates a sequence of doubles uniformly distributed in $[0, 1)$. Alternatively, normally distributed numbers could be generated using `numpy.random.randn`. Lastly, the created matrix should have a specifiable matrix condition number, since it indicates how bad the numerical properties of the matrix are, which impacts the stability of all algorithms.

The test matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ with $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^x$, $x \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ and $m \geq n$ is constructed as follows

$$A = QDW^T \quad (4.1)$$

The matrices are equivalent to the SVD $A = U\Sigma V^T$, with

$$\begin{aligned} U &:= QW \\ \Sigma &:= D \\ V &:= W \end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

The extra W operator in Equation (4.2) is a remnant of previous construction methods. However, $A = QDW^T$ only has the benefits, that it takes less computational time to calculate, and it causes less error propagation during the construction. The two matrices $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ and $W \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are generated with the specified sizes and the seeds s and $s + 1$ respectively. Afterwards all entries

of Q and W are shifted by -0.5 , such that the values are uniformly distributed in $[-0.5, 0.5)$, so that negative numbers are also included. Finally, the matrices are orthogonalized using `numpy.linalg.qr`.

The diagonal matrix $D \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is constructed in Equation (4.3), such that it fulfills the required matrix condition number.

$$D = \begin{bmatrix} 10^{x \frac{0}{n-1}} & & & \\ & 10^{x \frac{1}{n-1}} & & \\ & & \ddots & \\ & & & 10^{x \frac{n-1}{n-1}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.3)$$

For $n = 1$, it is not possible to create ill conditioned matrices. Since the smallest and largest singular value are the same, the condition number is always 1.

Since the construction is also affected by computer arithmetic, the required matrix condition number can most definitely not be achieved for $x > \frac{1}{\epsilon}$. Moreover, the matrix can become de facto rank deficient.

Another problem is that, for the same size $m \times n$ and seed s and varying matrix condition number the structure of the matrix stays, but the matrix condition number itself is just scaled. A possible fix for the future might be to use a new seed, like

$$s' = \text{hash}((m + n + \text{cond}) * s)$$

instead.

4.2. Software installation, System and miscellaneous Options

The versions of the most important packages and the system specifications can be found in Appendix A.

The python environment was created and managed using `pyenv-virtualenv`¹ and `pyenv-virtualenvwrapper`². Both of which are part of [23]. Download and installation was done according to the installation guides. Python version 3.8.10 was used³.

For pyMOR, a modified version of the release [9] was used. The modified version can be found in [5]. The installation of necessary packages for pyMOR was done according to the documentation. NumPy uses OpenBLAS as reference BLAS, and its matrices are stored in C-major order.

All calculations were performed on a Dell PowerEdgeR7525 Rack Server with two AMD EPYC 7763 64 - Core Processor and two NUMA nodes with each around 500 GB of

¹<https://github.com/pyenv/pyenv-virtualenv>

²<https://github.com/pyenv/pyenv-virtualenvwrapper>

³Originally it was planned to include benchmarks with the FEniCS backend. As of August 14, 2024, the latest available FEniCS version is `fenics 2019.1.0`, when installing it using `pip`. In order for it to work properly a python version < 3.9 was used.

memory. Refer to Appendix A for more details about the cache layout. Each CPU has 64 physical cores, or 128 virtual/logical cores. The CPU uses a concept called Hyper-threading⁴. Every physical core is architecturally adjusted to provide registers for two threads and their meta-data, which allows for a faster swap between those two threads. The threads still have to share the same cache and computational units (e.g. ALU and FPU). Because of this, CPU's with Hyper-threading have two virtual cores for every physical core.

The calculating process is limited to NUMA node 0 to avoid increased latency, due to data accesses across NUMA nodes. The scheduler could potentially move a thread including its memory back and forth between NUMA nodes for load balancing reasons. On this system NUMA node 0 includes the virtual cores 0-64 and 128-191.

Before every measurement the garbage collector is called, to clear all unreachable objects, and during the measurement deactivated.

The used server is set up as a multiuser system. Therefore, there is no guarantee, that all measurements were unaffected by other users.

For benchmarking the QR decomposition, a test matrix is created and used for all of them. For the pyMOR functions, the matrix has to be wrapped in a `NumpyVectorArray`, and the resulting Q unwrapped⁵. Since the NumPy QR implementation does not offer the option, to overwrite the input matrix with the data of Q , all variants are set up to take a copy of the input, which is their default setting. Taking the copy is therefore included in the runtime measurement.

The pyMOR based variants have a tolerance, which is set to 10^{-13} by default. However, SCQR and the Gram-Schmidt based algorithms use this tolerance for different purposes. The Gram-Schmidt variants measure the length of the currently projected vector and remove it, if it is below the given tolerance. As one will be able to see in Chapter 6, this does have implications on the relative reconstruction residual and the subspace angle. Shifted Choleksy QR, on the other hand, calculates the loss of orthogonality in every iteration using

$$\|Q^T Q - I\|_F \quad (4.4)$$

The Frobenius norm has a lower runtime. In case the norm is still higher compared to the tolerance, another iteration is performed (As long as the maximum number of iterations is not reached).

Revision note: The removal of linearly dependent or zero vectors, given the mentioned tolerances, is incorrectly implemented for all classical Gram-Schmidt variants, that are going to be presented. Because of this, vectors are not removed and all their measurements are incorrect. It is to be expected that the classical Gram-Schmidt variants have a similar or worse behaviour compared to the PGS variants. In particular the relative reconstruction residual for ill conditioned matrices would be affected by the removal of those vectors (c.f. with PGS variants in Chapter 6).

⁴The Hyper-Threading Technology is a simultaneous multithreading (SMT) technique. The name itself is a Intel trademark.

⁵The matrix R is just a `numpy.ndarray`

4.3. Benchmarking prototype

I developed a tool for this thesis, which allowed me to collect and manage metrics for many parameters more efficiently. The idea and requirements developed over multiple iterations towards the current proof of concept.

The idea was to create a tool, which offers all functionality through a base class. The user has to define in the inheriting class all variables and their domains/values, and implement an abstract function. This function has to take one tuple of the Cartesian product of the variables as parameters. Further on this tuple will be called a 'data point'. The output of the function is a tuple containing the metrics⁶. Once the script is started as main, a method of the base class is called, which handles the input parameters of the process. For every variable a flag for the process parameters is created. The user can utilize these flags to select values or ranges of the variable. By default, all values of a variable are selected. At the moment, this is done by indexing every value. This also allows indexing of the data points. It is also possible to skip all selections up to a specific index, using `-skip_until`. This can be used in case the process has to be restarted. It requires the user to know the desired index.

This selection of values is important, since many operations perform based on it. For example, the pre-defined flag `-e` starts the execution of the benchmark. It 'lazy evaluates' the Cartesian product of the selected values of the variables and calls the function sequentially. It collects the output and directly stores it in a serialized file, which is created using the python package pickle. With the flag `-t` the number of repetitions can be selected, which at the moment has to be used by the user's implementation in the function. In case the same data points get evaluated multiple times, for every metric of the output a list is created, and the values stored accordingly. This allows for reduce functions, like taking the median of the metrics. Since in between the iterations the current indexes get logged, the flag `-skip_until` becomes usable.

The flag `-cpu` can be used to index and limit the cores, that are used by the process. This is done using the python interface for `sched_set_affinity`.

With flags, like `-print`, the collected metrics of the selected data points get printed to the terminal. `-delete` allows deleting the selected data points from the data file. This is useful in cases, where an algorithm gets modified, and previous results are not needed anymore.

Other useful flags, that can be used together, are `-csv_path`, `-csv` and `-merge`. The first one is straight forward, it allows specifying a path, at which the `.csv` is stored. The second flag can be used to define the order of variables for the `.csv` output. The rows are defined by the values of the first variable, and the columns by the Cartesian product of the other variables. The user can further specify the desired values by simply selecting them, using the flags for the variables. The flag `-merge`⁷ allows selecting variables. Data points along those variables get merged, and a single data point is created, containing all the metrics. This was in our case useful for the variable 'seed', since metric differences over the seed are expected to be small. Lastly, a reduce function, like minimum, maximum, average, median or sum, has to be applied. This is implemented by use of the python package `xarray`⁸. It uses the `numpy.ndarray`.

⁶The tuple is wrapped in another class called `DataPoint`, which is created by the class `DataPointDescriptor`, containing the names of the metrics

⁷A more suitable name would be `-reduce`

⁸[14, 15]

It allows separate names for every dimension and its indexes. One can interact with the matrix using those names. This simplified the code greatly.

Problems and possible Improvements

This approach reduces the boilerplate code immensely, since only the variables and the function have to be implemented. It directly allows a flexible use of the script and manages the data. In order to exchange measurements only two files (the script and the data file) have to be exchanged. Additionally, the tool has to be installed in a virtual python environment.

Nevertheless, this prototype is still flawed and a lot of improvements can be done. Papers, like [4] and [3] provide guidelines and best practices for benchmarking. Of which, many coincide with the encountered problems of the tool, which will be discussed in following, together with current problems of the tool itself. The paper [3] focuses mostly on, how to define the goal of a benchmark, to categorize the problem, how to design suitable problems for algorithms and how to evaluate the measurements. It was not possible to analyze and apply suggestions from the paper to the tool and include it in this thesis.

At the moment the tool is highly undocumented and untested, since it is just a proof of concept. Which is bad practice in general and makes it unnecessarily hard to work on in the future. The class and/or function names might also be misleading.

The main usage of this tool is to run QR decompositions. For some parameters the runtime can be up to 50 minutes long. Because of this, micro benchmarks were never considered. However, for some matrix shapes the runtime is less than a second. Those short runs are especially affected by other processes, the operating system, and the state of the hardware (e.g. CPU clock speed and temperature).

Moreover, I do not verify, that all modules and packages are correctly loaded on benchmark start. I thought it would be enough to run the script once for some parameters, to let python compile the code and store it in .pyc files in the `__pycache__` directories of the modules. However, not all the compiled code is cached. Particularly, the main script itself.

It would be reasonable to implement at least test runs, that allow each algorithm to correctly load the modules, or even to implement an optional hardware warm up for to short runs.

Some requirements from [4] are covered. For example, I did deliberately only select CPU cores of the first NUMA node and used Hyper-threading (all virtual cores are selected). Nevertheless, during initial testing on a Intel i3 6006u⁹ I encountered problems, where the CPU affinity settings were ignored by NumPy and OpenBLAS, even, when setting it beforehand. The hardware allocation was unsuccessful and only noticed by chance. Setting `OMP_NUM_THREADS` additionally before importing NumPy can fix this. The behavior can be changed during the OpenBLAS installation using the `NO_AFFINITY=1` flag in the `makefile`¹⁰ or by setting the environment variable `OPENBLAS_MAIN_FREE=1`. Some BLAS implementations like MKL might offer more flexibility of handling affinity even during runtime.

In the paper it is mentioned, that setting the scheduler affinity¹¹ can be useless. A process can simply change the settings. They recommend using control groups (cgroups) of the Linux

⁹Skylake architecture

¹⁰<https://github.com/OpenMathLib/OpenBLAS/blob/v0.3.8/Makefile.rule#L145-L154>

¹¹In Chapter 3.4 and 5.1

operating systems, since it manages and tracks the selected process and its child processes. It can also be used to enforce limits on the memory usage. Furthermore, they propose limiting the view of a process onto the systems resources, by use of containers and namespaces. It does not affect the performance, but encapsulates the process further, which mitigates possible unpredictable side effects. In order to apply both suggestions, the benchmark has to be isolated even further. This means, that every run has to be a separate process. The developed tool could be modified to do this. In this case the called script (main) would simply create new child processes for every data point, with the difficulty being, to ensure that the process is successfully killed.

The current main use of the tool is to measure runtime and errors for the QR decompositions. Instantiating the test matrix for every run would be too expensive, since it can take up to 2 minutes. Instead, objects could be shared between runs by temporarily storing and loading it in a file. Another challenge would be to transfer measured metrics or even objects back to the main process. There are two possible options. Either using files to store the metrics or writing into the `stdin` of the main process. Moreover, during the benchmark the main process cannot busy wait, since it would impact the performance. Therefore, the main process would have to ‘sleep’ and get signaled once the benchmark run finishes, to become active again. So there needs to be some kind of synchronization. This is especially an issue, if the benchmark ends up in e.g. an infinite loop. So limiting the runtime is a necessity. The mentioned issues regarding synchronization between main and the child process gets worse, if other programming languages should also be supported by the tool. It would require in all of those languages interfaces, in order to simplify the setup, reduce boilerplate code and especially to mitigate user errors.

In the paper [4] the benchmarking framework `BENCHEXEC`¹² is introduced, which fulfills the mentioned, and more, guidelines. It might be possible to include `BENCHEXEC` into the tool and use it to handle the benchmark run. The main goal of the tool would become to manage the parameters and the output.

The CSV output is working, but requires due to inefficient usage of `xarray` too much memory. Moreover, it is at the moment inflexible and only allows one kind of output format. For example, for the surface plots in Section 4.4 the data had to be formatted with a separate script for `pgfplots`. However, also other output formats, like JSON or XML should be supported. Another important missing feature is the ability to visualize the selected data points directly, allowing the user to analyze the collected data immediately.

Furthermore, it is tedious to select the values for the variables. As an example¹³

```
python3 src/benchmarks/cr_qr_benchmark.py -a -size 25: -seed :4 -cond ::5 -fenics 0 -cpu :63
↪ 128:191 -t 2 -plw 1:3 6: -e
```

starts the runs also used for Chapter 7. Adding a history for the selection, with a possible option to modify them, would greatly improve the tool.

The data file contains a python dictionary (set of key/value pairs), which stores the data point under their unique ID’s. As an improvement a data format like `HDF5` could be used, since it can handle large data sets more efficiently. It is also supported in different programming languages.

¹²<https://github.com/sosy-lab/benchexec>

¹³The command is just for reference. The meaning is not relevant for the context

Currently, it is not possible to change the number of variables of the inheriting class, since they are used to parse the .pickle file. However, the order of the variables and their values can be adjusted. This requires, that each data point gets reindexed, since their unique ID changed. In practice, I specified more variables than needed as placeholder in case I want to modify the script and keep the data.

Lastly, a support for specifying variables as domains, instead of explicit values, would improve flexibility. The user could then select values using e.g. a formula. But it also has serious implications on the current code in regard to unique indexing. The user might want two values to be equal, but they are not, or vice versa.

4.4. Overview and outline of used plot/graph types

Three major categories of visualizations are used in the Chapters 5 to 7, which are introduced in the following. The test matrix will be constructed according to Section 4.1. The seeds used for the pseudo-random generated matrix will be specified in the caption of every plot, but will be limited between $\text{seed} \in \{0, 1, \dots, 4\}$. Due to time limitations mostly only one repetition was done. Because, in some instances, QR decompositions had a runtime of up to 50 minutes (cf. Chapter 6). The exact number will be specified in the caption of the plots. Furthermore, the construction of the test matrix and the calculation of the error metrics took in some cases (square matrices) up to 17 minutes. In total all runs combined took more than 1 month.

The median was taken over all runs with the same shape and matrix condition number, but different seed. Because of the difference in magnitudes for the inputs and the metrics calculated a base 10 log scale is used through out this thesis.

Over matrix condition number

The first category of plots will be called over matrix condition number, for which a matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ with $n = 10^4$ is used. Along the x-axis the matrix condition number will be increased in log scale with data points taken for the following values $\{10^0, 10^{2.5}, \dots, 10^{20}\}$. It is to be expected, that for higher matrix condition numbers the algorithms either return solutions with high errors, or break altogether. Especially for $\kappa_2(A) \geq \frac{1}{\epsilon}$ and $\kappa_2(A) \geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon}}$ it will be visible, that some variants are numerically unstable.

Figure 5.1 Figure 5.5 Figure 6.1 Figure 7.1 Figure C.1

Over matrix size-ratio

The second category, called over matrix size-ratio will instead have a fixed matrix condition number of 10^{20} and the matrix size-ratio will vary along the x-axis in log scale. With matrix size-ratio $\frac{m}{n}$ with $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, $m \cdot n = 10^8$, $m \geq n$ is meant, which means that all matrices have the same number of entries, but the shape changes drastically from a matrix with a single vector to a square matrix. The goal was to find out and compare the impact of the shape onto the errors, data volume loaded into the caches and also partially the runtime. Since the time complexity for all algorithms is $O(mn^2)$ the runtime will increase drastically. Alternatively, $m \cdot n^2$ could have been kept constant to observe possible fluctuation in the runtime due to side effects of BLAS and data blocks fitting in the cache.

The Table B.1 was added, containing all the (m, n) pairs and their size-ratios, to simplify lookup of the matrix shape.

Figure 5.2 Figure 5.4 Figure 6.2 Figure 7.2 Figure C.2

Surface plot

The last type of plot with the name Surface plot shows for every QR decomposition algorithm and metric a top-down 2D surface plot showing both results for varying matrix condition number and matrix size-ratio along the y and x axes respectively.

The values in each surface plot are represented by a color from a color map, which has its limitations. Additionally, the values between data points are bilinearly interpolated, creating artificial data points. Therefore, looking into the .csv files is recommended.

Figure 5.3 Figure 5.6 Figure 5.7 Figure 5.8 Figure 6.3 Figure 6.3

Chapter 5.

Shifted Cholesky QR decomposition implementation and benchmarks

This chapter explains problems and observations that occurred during the development of the Shifted Cholesky QR implementation in pyMOR. All problems are related to the shift. Testing with the mentioned tool from Section 4.3 revealed, that SCQR is unstable for matrices with high matrix condition numbers. Additionally, the runtime increases drastically, if the matrix shape is close to a square, or a square matrix. All results are for the Euclidean inner product space. Therefore, Equation (3.5) will be defined as

$$s = 11(mn + n(n + 1))\mathbf{u}\|A\|_2^2 \quad (5.1)$$

for simplicity. Non-Euclidean inner product spaces are still a pyMOR specific issue. All of those topics are further discussed in Section 5.1, Section 5.3 and Section 5.4 respectively.

5.1. Shift Strategies

In Algorithm 4.2 from the paper [10], iterations and shifts can be repeated as many times, as required for a desired loss of orthogonality. The shift is fixed and can effectively be calculated just once.

However, the algorithm fails for high matrix condition numbers, even with a maximum number of 10 iterations. Due to a misinterpretation of the paper by myself I tested out a variant, where the shift is recalculated instead, by calculating the norm of the Gramian, which changes in every iteration. This increased the runtime in some cases drastically, but seemed to be more stable than the original counterpart. Since this new variant is mathematically unproven the pyMOR main developers decided to follow the version from the paper for now and add it to the newest release 2024.1.0.

The prototype implementation was designed to apply the shift onto the Gramians diagonal in a while True loop, until the Cholesky decomposition is successful. However, in some cases, in an iteration > 1 , the calculated norm and therefore shift was by magnitudes lower than machine epsilon. This low shift caused some kind of infinite loop, since it had to be applied potentially thousands of times, or more. Therefore, one has to add a minimum shift. In case the calculated shift is smaller than machine epsilon it is set machine epsilon.

Important to note for the plots in this section is, that the shift for both versions is calculated using the sparse and Hermitian eigenvalue solver `scipy.sparse.linalg.eigsh` from SciPy, since it proofed to be the best option, which will be explained and shown in the next section. Also, as mentioned in Section 4.2, all SCQR variants have a tolerance of 10^{-13} for the loss of orthogonality. Until the criteria are fulfilled SCQR performs more iterations up to the specified maximum 10 iterations.

Figure 5.1.: Comparison between recalculated and fixed shift SCQR variant. Both variants use eigsh with a tolerance of 10^{-4} to estimate the norm of the Gramian. Over matrix condition number plot for $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ with $n = 10^4$ generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.

Since the plots are going to be explained in more detail in Section 5.3 the focus in this section will be to highlight the difference between recalculating and not recalculating the shift in every iteration.

5.1.1. Over matrix condition number

In Figure 5.1 one can see, that up to a matrix condition number of $10^{7.5}$ both variants perform mostly the same in terms of runtime and errors.

As it was visible in Equation (3.4), the matrix condition number of the Gramian is the squared condition number of A . Hence, one can see an increase in runtime for $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{10}$, since the condition number of the Gramian is larger than $\frac{1}{\epsilon}$. This increase in runtime is caused by more iterations required to achieve orthogonality. Since the recalculation of the shift requires more

Figure 5.2.: Comparison between recalculated and fixed shift SCQR variant. Both variants use eigsh with a tolerance of 10^{-4} to estimate the norm of the Gramian. Over matrix size-ratio plot for $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$ generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.

time, this variant has a higher runtime compared to the fixed shift variant. The errors of both variants deviate within tolerances.

For $\kappa_2(A) > 10^{10}$ the fixed shift variant performs 10 iterations and raises an internal exception, since the tolerance for orthogonality was not reached. Therefore, no errors could be calculated, and the runtime is also lost because of the implementation in the tool. Meanwhile, the variant with recalculated shift still returns results with relatively small errors. For reference, for $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$ the recalculated shift variant requires 6 shift calculations and has a runtime of 42.56 s and achieves a loss of orthogonality of $\approx 10^{-14.55}$.

Increasing the number of data points especially between $10^{7.5} \leq \kappa_2(A) \leq 10^{10}$ would greatly improve those statements.

Figure 5.3.: Comparison between recalculated and fixed shift SCQR variant. Both variants use eigsh with a tolerance of 10^{-4} to estimate the norm of the Gramian. For the variants the runtime and error metrics are visualized. Surface plot with varying matrix size-ratio on the x-axis and matrix condition number on the y-axis generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.

5.1.2. Over matrix size-ratio

In the plot in Figure 5.2 the matrix condition number is always high with a value of $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$. Both variants have an error of 0 for the error metrics in the case $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) = 8$, which results in the data points not being shown in the log plots.

As seen in the previous plot the fixed shift variant should not be returning results for this high of a matrix condition number. However, for a matrix size-ratio $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) > 6.6$ the Gramian is e.g. of dimension $A^T A \in \mathbb{R}^{5 \times 5}$. Therefore, numerical errors might not accumulate too much and the fixed shift Shifted Cholesky QR still manages to return results. For the parameters the fixed shift version does work, it mostly has slightly lower errors compared to the recalculated shift variant. Nevertheless, the fixed shift variant is unstable in all the other cases, that are also more meaningful compared to matrices with only up to 5 columns.

5.1.3. Surface plot

In a better overview in Figure 5.3 as a summary it is clear, that both variants perform mostly the same except for $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) < 6.6$ and $\kappa_2(A) > 10^{10}$, for which the fixed shift variant is unstable, with some exceptions. It is not always obvious in the plot, but in the cases where the fixed shift variant works, it returns equal or better results than the recalculated shift variant with a slightly lower runtime.

Iteration	Norm estimate	Calculated shift	Applied shift	Loss of Orthogonality
1	9.9999e+19	4.8852e+33	4.8852e+33	99.9999
2	2.0446e-14	2.0423e-34	2.2204e-16	93.8089
3	0.9892	4.7809e-07	4.7809e-07	75.1013
4	-	-	-	0.0001
5	-	-	-	8.0291e-14

Table 5.1.: $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $n = 10^4$, $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{10}$

Iteration	Norm estimate	Calculated shift	Applied shift	Loss of Orthogonality
1	1.0000e+40	4.8852e+73	4.8852e+73	100.0000
2	2.0301e-34	2.0134e-74	2.2204e-16	100.0000
3	9.1950e-19	4.1304e-43	2.2204e-16	99.9954
4	0.0041	8.3513e-12	8.3513e-12	87.8466
5	0.9999	4.8851e-07	4.8851e-07	78.3544
6	0.9999	4.8851e-07	4.8851e-07	67.5410
7	0.9999	4.8852e-07	4.8852e-07	54.6271
8	-	-	-	1.6274e-05
9	-	-	-	7.5885e-14

Table 5.2.: $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $n = 10^4$, $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$

5.2. Recalculated shift values in iterations

The tables Table 5.1 and Table 5.2 contain the calculated norms, shifts and loss of orthogonality of all iterations, when applying SCQR onto two matrices with the matrix condition numbers $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{10}$ and $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$ respectively.

The norm estimate of the Gramian $\|X\|_2$ is calculated using `eigsh` $1e-4$. This will be further explained in Section 5.3. The applied shift has a lower limit, defined by

$$s := \begin{cases} s & s \geq \varepsilon \\ \varepsilon & s < \varepsilon \end{cases}$$

The loss of orthogonality during the SCQR calculations was evaluated using

$$\|Q^T Q - I\|_F$$

The Frobenius norm is used to define a faster to compute termination criterion.

The Cholesky decomposition did not fail in the last two iterations. Therefore, no norm and shift was calculated. The matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ with $n = 10^4$ generated with seed 0 has a matrix condition number $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{10}$ in the first table and $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$ in the second.

As it can be seen, the norm estimate varies by magnitudes between iterations. In particular between the first and second iteration. It might be interesting to consider evaluating the norm in the first iteration and applying different shifting strategies depending on the magnitude further on.

In both tables the second evaluated shift is less than machine epsilon (without the minimum shift it would cause an infinite loop), after a significant shift in the first iteration. Instead of

calculating the norm in the second and possibly higher iterations, directly applying a shift with ε might be more runtime efficient with similar errors. Applying a machine epsilon shift too often should not cause any problems, since it is so low.

Using different tolerances or even norms for different iterations is also an option. Recording and visualizing the data in the tables for more data points or even all, that were already considered, could greatly improve these assumptions and should be done in further benchmarks.

5.3. SCQR norm calculation

During the implementation of Shifted Choleksy QR in pyMOR the norm of the matrix A , which is required for the shift, was initially calculated with $X = A^T A$ and the function call

```
normEstimate = scipy.linalg.norm(X, 2)
```

which uses an SVD internally¹.

One reason why one can take the norm of the Gramian is because it is in most cases smaller than A . Furthermore, pyMOR stores the Gramian in a `numpy.ndarray`, so implementations based on the `VectorArray` interface can be avoid. The reason why one can choose between these two options in the first place is due to Equation (5.2).

$$\begin{aligned} \|A\|_2^2 &= \|A^T A\|_2 \\ &= \|X\|_2 \end{aligned} \tag{5.2}$$

Note the power of two for the norm of A . The equality can be better understood when looking at the singular value decomposition of $A = U\Sigma V^T$. The diagonal matrix Σ contains all singular values of A and therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \|A\|_2^2 &= \sigma_{\max}(A)^2 \\ &= \sigma_{\max}(\Sigma)^2 \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, when proving the equation from the other side with

$$\begin{aligned} \|A^T A\|_2 &= \|(U\Sigma V^T)^T U\Sigma V^T\|_2 \\ &= \|V\Sigma^T U^T U\Sigma V^T\|_2 \\ &= \|V\Sigma^T U^{-1} U\Sigma V^T\|_2 \\ &= \|V\Sigma^T \Sigma V^T\|_2 \\ &= \|V\Sigma^2 V^T\|_2 \end{aligned} \tag{5.3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sigma_{\max}(\Sigma^2) \\ &= \sigma_{\max}(\Sigma)^2 \end{aligned} \tag{5.4}$$

one can show that $\|A\|_2^2 = \|A^T A\|_2$.

However, during testing I found out that in some cases the runtime of the Shifted Choleksy QR was unsatisfactory. Using the python tool `cProfile` I was able to pinpoint the problem to the NumPy norm calculation, which led me to try out alternatives.

¹<https://github.com/numpy/numpy/blob/maintenance/1.24.x/numpy/linalg/linalg.py#L2342-L2592>

5.3.1. Eigenvalue solvers

Following the steps from Equation (5.3) results in

$$\begin{aligned}A^T A &= V \Sigma^2 V^T \\ &= V \Sigma^2 V^{-1}\end{aligned}$$

and using the definition of ‘similar matrices’²

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda_{\max}(A^T A) &= \lambda_{\max}(V \Sigma^2 V^T) \\ &= \lambda_{\max}(V \Sigma^2 V^{-1}) \\ &= \lambda_{\max}(\Sigma^2)\end{aligned}$$

The eigenvalues of diagonal and triangular matrices are on the diagonal itself. This results in $\lambda_i = \sigma_i^2$, and therefore $\|A^T A\|_2 = \lambda_{\max}(A^T A)$.

Because of this, one can use the eigensolvers `scipy.linalg.eigh` and `scipy.sparse.linalg.eigsh` from SciPy. In the following they will be referred to as `eigh` and `eigsh`, respectively. Both functions work on symmetric matrices, which is the case for $X = A^T A$.

The function calls in Section 5.3.1 are set up such that they only return the largest eigenvalue. Both of them return eigenvectors by default, which are not of interest for computing the shift.

```
normEstimate = scipy.linalg.eigh(  
    X,  
    eigvals_only=True,  
    subset_by_index=[n-1,n-1], # to calculate only the largest eigenvalue  
    driver='evr'  
)[0]  
  
normEstimate = scipy.sparse.linalg.eigsh(  
    X,  
    k=1,  
    tol=tol,  
    return_eigenvectors=False  
)
```

`eigh` is a wrapper for LAPACK routines³. The driver `evr`⁴, or more specific for doubles the function uses `dsyevr`. It uses the Multiple Relatively Robust Representation (MRRR) algorithm to calculate eigenvalues for dense matrices.

`eigsh` on the other hand relies on the subroutines `SSEUPD` or `DSEUPD` from [17] to perform the Implicitly Restarted Lanczos Method⁵. It is designed to handle sparse matrices, and it allows the user to specify a relative tolerance (`tol`) between the eigenvalue and eigenvalue estimate, which defaults to ε . The correct choice for a tolerance will be explained later on. This function only works on the real data types `float` and `double`. The original Lanczos Method can be unstable. In those cases it will not converge. The Implicitly Restarted Lanczos Method tries to mitigate this.

²pp. 66-67 in [12]

³<https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy/reference/generated/scipy.linalg.eigh.html>

⁴https://netlib.org/lapack/explore-html/d1/d56/group__heevr.html

⁵<https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy/reference/generated/scipy.sparse.linalg.eigsh.html>

However, it might still be a good idea to have a backup routine to calculate a norm estimate in case it fails. `eigsh` has an optional starting vector `v0`, which defaults to a random vector. Since no starting vector or seed is directly set for this function, it violates repeatability. Because of this, fluctuation in runtime and error metrics were observed between different runs with the same parameters. Since the median of a few runs is taken it does not affect the results too much.

5.3.2. Frobenius norm

Another idea was to use other norms, like the Frobenius norm, since it should have a lower calculation time. Moreover, testing the Frobenius norm on the Gramian can also provide insights when applying it to the non-Euclidean inner product matrix B . This norm can result in a lot of numerical errors, since it has to add up all squares of all matrix entries. In the paper the coefficients for the shift are proven using the 2-norm. Proving it starting with the Frobenius norm would have exceeded the scope of this thesis. However, due to the Frobenius norm being bounded by the norm equivalence Equation (2.20) and expected runtime being of more interest, it was not necessary to prove it in the first place. Instead, I considered different cases and covered the boundaries of the equivalence for testing purposes.

Frobenius (fro)

In case $\|X\|_2 \approx \|X\|_F$.

```
normEstimate = numpy.linalg.norm(X, 'fro')
```

Frobenius upper boundary (fro u)

In case $\|X\|_F \approx \sqrt{n}\|X\|_2$. The idea is, if the Frobenius norm of the matrix is close to the upper boundary, the norm is divide by an additional \sqrt{n} to achieve $\frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}\|X\|_F \approx \|X\|_2$.

```
normEstimate = numpy.linalg.norm(X, 'fro') / numpy.sqrt(n)
```

Frobenius lower boundary fro l

This case is based on the wrong assumption, that the norm equivalence between 2-norm and Frobenius norm is given by

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}\|A^T A\|_2 \leq \|A^T A\|_F \leq \sqrt{n}\|A^T A\|_2$$

This led to the additional case $\|X\|_F \approx \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}\|X\|_2$ and therefore $\sqrt{n}\|X\|_F \approx \|X\|_2$

```
normEstimate = numpy.linalg.norm(X, 'fro') * numpy.sqrt(n)
```

This variant is flawed and will in some cases shift with a factor of up to 100 ($= \sqrt{10000}$) times more. It is still added nonetheless, since it provides insights into the impact of a too large shift.

5.3.3. Over matrix size-ratio

Starting off with the varying matrix size-ratio plot Figure 5.4. It is important to note, that with decreasing size-ratio the size of the Gramian increases. Therefore, it is to be expected, that the runtime increases as well, since the Cholesky decomposition, norm and the inverse of a larger matrix have to be computed.

Leaving out the single vector matrix case, this behavior can be observed for $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \geq 10^{1.59}$. In that range the runtime increases from 1.7 s to 7.9 s. Looking into the relative speedup, one can see that for those size-ratios all algorithms perform mostly the same. The largest speedup can be observed for eigsh 1e-1 at $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \approx 10^{1.59}$ with a value of 1.76. The order changes in the plot a few times. This can definitely be caused by the low number of repetitions per data point. However, eigsh with a tolerance of $\{10^{-1}, \dots, 10^{-4}\}$ seems to be consistently faster than the others.

That said, it is hard to miss that the behavior changes drastically for $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) < 10^{1.59}$. All variants do have a significant increase in runtime. Yet, it is by far less compared to the 2-norm. With a runtime of 702.98 s for the square case it is up to 16.5 times slower than eigsh 1e-4, which has a runtime of just 42.56 s. In the relative speedup plot it is already visible between $10^{1.59} < \log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \leq 10^{1.01}$, that the speedup of the 2-norm variant shrinks, before it becomes the slowest algorithm compared to the others. Even though the matrix size has a fixed size of 0.8 GB, the size of the Gramian varies immensely from just 8 Bytes in the single vector case all the way up to 0.8 GB for the square matrix case. A full list of the Gramians memory sizes can be found in Table B.1. This is most certainly the reason for the increase in runtime. At some points the different cache levels are too small, to store most of the Gramian. Here I will only focus on the cache levels L1, L2 and L3. The used system has the L1 caches split into a dedicated data (L1D) and instructions (L1I) caches. The data access latency increases exponentially for higher cache levels, since the cache is physically further away from the cores. Because of this, larger caches can be used for higher cache levels. The prefetcher tries to predict which data and instructions are required at a certain point of time. It loads the data beforehand into the caches. A ‘cache miss’ is an event, which is caused by not preloaded data.

When further looking into the system specifications of the used system (cf. Appendix A), One can see, that one NUMA node has in total 256 MB, 32.768 MB and 2.048 MB of memory in the L3, L2 and L1I,L1D caches respectively. Considering an idealistic scenario, in which all cache levels can be used to store just the Gramian, which is $8 \cdot n^2$ Byte large. For $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \approx 10^{2.6}$ the Gramian does not fit into the L1D caches, $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \approx 10^{1.4}$ not into L2 and $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \approx 10^{0.5}$ in L3.

Right between the L2 and L3 caches being too small to fit the Gramian, the runtime of all algorithms starts to increase significantly. Especially the 2-norm, which uses an SVD to calculate the largest singular value is affected the most. It is not the correct algorithm to use in the first place, since it does not utilize the symmetry of the Gramian unlike the symmetric eigenvalue solvers. It has an error of 0 for the single vector case. As mentioned in Section 4.1, in this case the matrix has always a condition number of 1. Since the Q matrix is calculated by $Q = AR^{-1}$,

Figure 5.4.: Comparison between SCQR variants with different norm estimation algorithms. Over matrix size-ratio plot for $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$ generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.

it is to be expected, that the relative reconstruction residual is low. The slight increase over the matrix size-ratio shrinking might be due to the increasing size of R and the Gramian, which results in more numerical errors. `fro 1` is as expected unstable and fails for matrix size-ratios $\frac{m}{n} \leq 10^3$. `fro` fails for the square matrix case, also the subspace angle calculation failed for it.

The subspace angle drops for the square matrix case. This is due to the fact, that there can only be an angle between subspaces for square matrices, if at least one of the matrices is rank deficient. The small error spikes around $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \approx 6.8$ and $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \approx 5.6$ for the subspace angle and relative reconstruction residual are probably also related to the matrix structure.

5.3.4. Over matrix condition number

In Figure 5.5 all variants have almost the same runtime for $\kappa_2(A) \leq 10^{7.5}$. For those condition numbers multiple iterations are done, however no shift has to be calculated yet. Moreover, for $\kappa_2(A) \approx 1$ the matrix is already orthogonal, which results in the low runtime. Therefore, in theory, all algorithms are executing the same code, since the norm is not evaluated. However, in both the runtime and in the relative speedup plots it is visible, that `eigh` is the slowest variants in most cases. The runs for `eigh` were done at a later point in time and were probably affected by something unknown. However, it does not change the overall picture since this ambiguous overhead seems to be constant by up to 2 seconds.

As expected, a matrix condition number of $\kappa_2(A) \geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon}}$ causes problems. The Gramian has a matrix condition number of above machine epsilon. This causes the matrix to be de facto singular, and the Cholesky decomposition fails. Therefore, a shift has to be calculated, which causes the increase in runtime. Even higher matrix condition numbers require more iterations and shifts, which can also be seen in Section 5.2.

Many of the variants have a consistent relative speedup in relation to the 2-norm variant for $\kappa_2(A) \geq 10^{10}$. Some of them, however, clearly have inconsistencies and perform more iterations compared to the 2-norm, `eigh` and most `eigsh` variants. `fro 1` for example performs for $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{12.5}$ all 10 iterations. The calculated shift is too large causing high errors. `fro` also requires more iterations for $\kappa_2(A) \geq 10^{15}$, but less than 10, to achieve an orthogonal Q . `eigsh 1e-5` and `eigsh 1e-6` might suggest, that they also need more iterations, but this might not be the case. It is more likely, that the higher tolerance requires more iterations inside the eigenvalue calculation, which causes them to deviate from the others. Again, for the relevant variants the errors are relatively low and consistent. `fro u` is stable, while `fro` is unstable for $\kappa_2(A) \geq 10^{17.5}$ `fro 1` already fails for $\kappa_2(A) \geq 10^{12.5}$.

5.3.5. Surface plot

When looking at the surface plots in Figure 5.6 and Figure 5.7 it is hard to spot any major differences, especially for the errors, since all variants perform mostly the same. For instance, even `fro 1` seems to have similar errors compared to the other variants, except for $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) < 4$ and $\kappa_2(A) < 10^{10}$. Also, `fro` seems to be stable except for square matrices with high matrix condition numbers. However, `fro u` should in my opinion be preferred out of all Frobenius norm variants, since it results in a shift lower or equal to the 2-norm based variants. A larger shift can cause more harm than good, which can be seen in `fro 1`'s case. Despite that, the limited amount of test runs does not guarantee, that `fro u` will always be stable. Possibly, in

Figure 5.5.: Comparison between SCQR variants with different norm estimation algorithms. Over matrix condition number plot for $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ with $n = 10^4$ generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.

Figure 5.6.: Comparison 1/2 between SCQR variants with different norm estimation algorithms. For every variant the runtime and error metrics are visualized. Surface plot with varying matrix size-ratio on the x-axis and matrix condition number on the y-axis generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.

Figure 5.7.: Comparison 2/2 between SCQR variants with different norm estimation algorithms. For every variant the runtime and error metrics are visualized. Surface plot with varying matrix size-ratio on the x-axis and matrix condition number on the y-axis generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.

Figure 5.8.: Comparison between a few selected SCQR variants with different norm estimation algorithms. For the variants just the relative Speedup is plotted. Surface plot with varying matrix size-ratio on the x-axis and matrix condition number on the y-axis generated with seeds 0 and 1 with 2 iterations each.

some not considered edge case scenario, a too small shift could be calculated, which causes some unexpected behavior. Therefore, the eigenvalue solver variant `eigsh` with some tolerance between $\{10^{-1}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-3}, 10^{-4}\}$ should be preferred, especially, since the difference in runtime is marginal. This can further be seen in the relative speedup surface plots Figure 5.8.

As it can be better seen in the graphics Figure 5.4 and Figure 5.5 does a tolerance lower or equal to 10^{-5} decrease the runtime. No data was collected for it, but for a tolerance of 10^{-7} the runtime was by far worse than the runtime of the 2-norm variant and for a tolerance of 10^{-8} the eigenvalue solver did not converge, which causes an exception. It will most likely not work for even higher tolerances.

A few minor observations are, that the surface angle for the square matrix case consistently low is. The square matrix case is just an exception, which was already explained in Section 5.3.3 and since the over matrix condition number plots Figure 5.5 might be misleading, the errors do in fact increases with both decreasing size-ratio and condition number.

Furthermore, it is noticeable that there are some visible patterns between the 3 residual based error metrics. However, since the errors are consistently low only a few selected will be mentioned. For example the horizontal lines in the relative reconstruction and Cholesky residual plots for the condition numbers 10^{10} and $10^{17.5}$ with a matrix size-ratio of $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) < 6$, which is due to more iterations and shift done. This can be somewhat confirmed with the increases in the runtime surface plots and the over matrix condition number plot Figure 5.5. The low error in R is the direct cause for a low error in the relative reconstruction residual and vice versa a higher error in R is also visible in the reconstruction residual.

For $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) > 6$, however, it is unclear why exactly the error in R increases. It is possibly due to the small size. This makes the reconstruction less prone for errors, but affects the error in Q .

5.4. Shifted Choleksy QR with non-euclidian inner product

So far only the Euclidean inner product was considered. However, in some cases a non-euclidian inner product⁶ is used. Eigenvalue solvers, like `eigh` or `eigsh` from external packages, cannot be used on pyMOR matrices and operators. Moreover, all projections, using the inner product, are more expensive.

Currently, `pymor.algorithms.eigs.eigs` is the only eigenvalue solver in pyMOR. It is an Arnoldi based solver, which does not take advantage of the symmetry. Moreover, it also uses a QR decomposition internally. To further improve the runtime a pyMOR Lanczos eigenvalue solver, similar to `eigsh`, could be implemented. Another possible alternative can be the Frobenius norm similar to `fro_u`. It is significantly easier to compute, especially on distributed systems, since the Frobenius norm is communication avoiding. One caveat is, that the Frobenius norm is prone for numerical errors which might lead to instabilities.

Runs for the pyMOR thermal block demo with different QR implementations have not been added to this thesis. It uses a non-euclidian inner product, which causes a non-satisfactory runtime for SCQR. In some instances it can be up to 10 times slower compared to PGS. The main reason for it being, that internally the QR decomposition is called multiple times with

⁶Algorithm 5.1 from [10] is designed for non-Euclidean inner product spaces.

different matrices. The norm of B does not change, but it is evaluated in every call. Thus, it is necessary to be able to cache the norm of B .

Chapter 6.

QR decomposition benchmarks

In this chapter the benchmark results for the Gram-Schmidt and Householder based QR decompositions, and additionally the Shifted Choleksy QR variant `eigsh 1e-4`, are shown and analyzed. Some variants will seem highly unfavorable in the Sections 6.1 to 6.3. However, only one use-case, in which a matrix has to be orthogonalized fully, is highlighted. Therefore, for a final conclusion especially Section 6.4 has to be taken into consideration.

6.1. Over matrix condition number

Beginning with the errors in Figure 6.1, one can see that as expected CGS is highly unstable, because it loses orthogonality in Q exponentially. In some cases, for low matrix condition numbers, the vectors of the matrix Q might still be orthogonal or at least span the same space as A , since the subspace angle is low and comparable to the other variants. For $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{2.5}$ and $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{17.5}$ the calculation of the subspace angle fails. The error in the relative reconstruction error might look good for all tested condition numbers, however, this only means that $A \approx QR$. The error in Q and R are too high for $\kappa_2(A) > 10^{7.5}$, which makes it unsuitable for any application. The variant CGS P IRO is stable until $\kappa_2(A) < 10^{10}$. It probably fails for $\kappa_2(A) \approx \frac{1}{\sqrt{\varepsilon}}$ already. CGS IRO LS on the other hand is stable until $\kappa_2(A) \geq 10^{17.5}$. It might be, that it starts to fail for $\kappa_2(A) \approx \frac{1}{\varepsilon}$. Comparing the runtimes of all 3 variants both CGS IRO LS and CGS P IRO have almost the same runtime. They are twice as high compared to the plain CGS algorithm.

As it will also be possible to see later on, CGS IRO LS is superior compared to CGS and CGS P IRO in terms of errors. For this reason the other 2 variants will not be further discussed in this thesis, but still visualized for the reader to form their own opinions.

Continuing with the other variants, all of them are stable over the whole domain with the PGS variants as exceptions. As mentioned in Section 4.2, the tolerance causes problems and removes important vectors, which increases the errors. Setting it to 0 or ε would have improved the relative reconstruction residual for $\kappa_2(A) \geq 10^{15}$, which would also benefit the subspace angle. This is not visible for the other Gram-Schmidt variants. CGS is affected by numerics too much anyway, CGS P IRO is unstable for such high matrix condition numbers, which causes internal exceptions and CGS IRO LS is also unstable for condition numbers $\kappa_2(A) \geq \frac{1}{\varepsilon}$.

Looking at the runtime however, it becomes apparent, that this does not matter too much. Both PGS and PGS V with a runtime of up to 3032 s (51 min) and 2010 s (33 min) are by magnitudes slower compared to the 279 s runtime for CGS IRO LS, or even 21 s and 11 s for the NumPy and SciPy variants. They make the disadvantages of Modified Gram Schmidt very clear. CGS like algorithms can effectively orthogonalize the current vector in parallel against the already created basis while MGS alike cannot. The code is far more sequential, which results in some interesting observations done in Chapter 7. SCQR is for $\kappa_2(A) \leq 10^{7.5}$ faster than even the

SciPy QR. For higher matrix condition numbers more iterations and shift are required, which leads up to a runtime of 45 s.

For $\kappa_2(A) \approx 1$ the matrix A is already orthogonal. Both PGS variants do not run repeated (only one pass over all vectors), which results in the lower runtime. As already mentioned, both variants remove vectors with a length below some threshold, which also impacts the runtime slightly, since a vector has to be orthogonalized against fewer vectors.

6.2. Over Matrix size-ratio

Looking at Figure 6.2 one can clearly see the $O(mn^2)$ time complexity of the Gram-Schmidt based algorithms scaled by different factors. On average PGS V is 1.25 and CGS IRO LS is 3.85 times faster than PGS. For NumPy, SciPy and Shifted Choleksy QR the runtime seems to stagnate between $10^5 \leq \log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \leq 10^2$. This will further be looked at in Chapter 7. The relative speedup varies for them strongly over the changing size-ratio. The maximum relative speedups for SciPy, NumPy and SCQR are 202.5, 108.5 and 53 respectively. Surprisingly, the SciPy QR is in most cases twice as fast as NumPy QR, even though both of them rely on the LAPACK implementations. NumPy and SCQR are with some differences comparable in runtime for $5 \leq \log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \leq 0.4$.

More relevant for MOR is, however, a size-ratio of $5 \leq \log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \leq 3$ (for the current total of matrix entries). In the zoomed in runtime plot, which displays runtimes between one and ten seconds, one can still see, that PGS and PGS V are the slowest. However, in that range the SciPy QR variant is ‘only’ up to 10 times faster in relation to PGS. Moreover, the NumPy and SCQR are slower compared to PGS for $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \geq 5.59$ and $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \geq 5.2$ respectively. Furthermore, both of them are also slower compared to CGS IRO LS for $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \geq 3.79$. The latter is especially interesting, since it means that for 128 columns and less it is faster to use CGS IRO LS. It is questionable if this behavior is also the case for matrices with a different total of entries, e.g. $m \cdot n = 10^x$ with $5 \leq x \leq 10$. Additionally, the results depend on the used architecture and BLAS and LAPACK packages used. Moreover, it might be more appealing to look at some fixed n values and observe the change in runtime when varying m , to see again, if this order changes or not. Analyzing this is crucial for more accurate heuristics.

For $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$ one can observe, that CGS IRO LS is unstable. It is able to provide okay solutions only for some matrix shapes. The PGS V variant has slightly higher fluctuating errors in Q and R as a result of numerical errors accumulating. Only the Householder-QR variants achieve low subspace angles. Interestingly it fails to do so for $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) = 0.19$ ($A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, $m = 12500$, $n = 8000$), which might be related to the shape.

6.3. Surface plot

Figure 6.3 reveals that previous assumptions are indeed true. The problem of the tolerance for for both PGS variants is clearly visible in the relative reconstruction residual. PGS V has compared to the other variants a by 1 – 2 magnitudes higher error in Q and R . Furthermore, the runtime is still bad. So there is no benefit in using it.

CGS IRO LS is overall stable for $\kappa_2(A) \leq 10^{15}$. Comparing its runtime to e.g. SCQR and the Householder variants, it looks overall worse. However, as it was visible in Figure 6.2, cases exists, where CGS IRO LS is faster than SCQR and the NumPy implementation. This will be visualized in the relative speedup surface plot Figure 6.4.

The high subspace angle for low matrix size-ratios and high condition numbers seems unavoidable for all Gram-Schmidt based variants and Shifted Choleksy QR. In cases, where it is critical, that the subspace angle is low, a Householder QR decomposition would be necessary, which provides great solutions for all shapes except $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) = 0.19$. As long as the user is working with `NumpyVectorArray`'s it would be straight forward to use the SciPy QR implementation. Otherwise, converting back and forth between `VectorArray`'s and `numpy.ndarray` could work especially on shared memory systems, with a high overhead. This would most likely still be faster than both PGS variants.

As one can roughly see Figure 6.4, CGS IRO LS is faster compared to SCQR for $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \leq 6.19$ and for $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \leq 3.79$ and $\kappa_2(A) \geq 10$. SCQR and the Householder variants show similar behavior for $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) > 6.19$. Shifted Choleksy QR excels in particular for low matrix condition numbers. On average SciPy seems to perform the best. For the pyMOR context, however, both SCQR and CGS IRO LS (or other CGS2 algorithm) might complement each other. Further research has to be done in order to find more precise boundaries for the speedup, since it is still unclear, how both behave on systems with lower specifications and smaller matrix sizes. Furthermore, looking on fixed n and varying m should be preferred, instead of the matrix size-ratio used for this thesis, since the same matrix size for a different total of entries has less correlation.

6.4. Over Columns to Orthogonalize

The three plots, with the matrix size-ratios $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \in \{0, 2, 4\}$, presented in Figure 6.5, show how the runtime increases as k -many vectors have to be orthogonalized against an existing orthogonal basis with $n - k$ vectors. In particular $k = 1$ is of interest, since it is widely used in pyMOR.

For clarification, the input matrix $A = [a_1, \dots, a_n]$ is generated as usual. Afterwards $n - k$ vectors are orthogonalized, resulting in the matrix $A' = [q_1, \dots, q_{n-k}, a_{n-k+1}, \dots, a_n]$ where q_i denotes the already orthonormal vectors. Afterwards the QR decomposition is started for the matrix A' and an offset of $n - k$. Only the last k vectors have to be orthogonalized.

Both NumPy and SciPy qr do not have an interface to specify an offset $n - k$. As a replacement the SciPy function `scipy.linalg.qr_insert` is used. The PGS V variant, for a yet unknown reason, does not provide an orthogonal Q , and is therefore excluded. Since CGS IRO LS splits the two orthogonalization steps onto 2 iterations, the number of vectors k to orthogonalize has to be increased to $k + 2$. For the other Gram-Schmidt based variants the implementation is straight forward. Because the SCQR implementation is slightly more complex it will not be explained in this thesis and instead referred to the implementation in [5].

In Figure 6.5 one can see, that using PGS for orthogonalizing a single vector works okay. It is never the fastest variant, but unlike in Figure 6.2 the discrepancy is not too large. This changes drastically for $k > 1$, since it has such a poor scaling. Both SciPy's `qr_insert` and SCQR are slower compared to CGS IRO LS, up to some k , which depends on the size-ratio. This is another

case, in which CGS IRO LS excels. However, more research would be required, to define a precise heuristic, for when to use it instead of SCQR.

Figure 6.1.: Comparison between QR variants. Over matrix condition number plot for $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ with $n = 10^4$ generated with seeds $\{0, 1, \dots, 4\}$ with 1 iteration each.

Figure 6.2.: Comparison between QR variants. Over matrix size-ratio plot for $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$ generated with seeds $\{0, 1, \dots, 4\}$ with 1 iteration each.

Figure 6.3.: Comparison between QR variants. For every variant the runtime and error metrics are visualized. Surface plot with varying matrix size-ratio on the x-axis and matrix condition number on the y-axis generated with seeds $\{0, 1, \dots, 4\}$ with 1 iteration each.

Figure 6.4.: Comparison between a few selected QR decomposition variants. For the variants just the relative Speedup is plotted. Surface plot with varying matrix size-ratio on the x-axis and matrix condition number on the y-axis generated with seeds $\{0, 1, \dots, 4\}$ with 1 iteration each.

Figure 6.5.: Comparison between QR variants. Just the runtime is plotted along the y-axis. Plots for matrices with size-ratios $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \in \{0, 2, 4\}$ and condition number $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{7.5}$ generated with seeds $\{0, 1, \dots, 4\}$ with 1 iterations each. Along the x-axis the number of columns orthogonalized against an already existing orthonormal basis is specified.

Chapter 7.

Performance monitoring

The following chapter is about measuring hardware related metrics, in order to learn more about the behavior and possible bottlenecks of the algorithms. In particular, I was interested in the number of cores used, cache miss related metrics and the number of clock cycles done per instruction. I also measured bandwidth and loaded/offloaded data volume of the RAM and prefetcher, which can be found in Appendix C. Performance monitoring is done by initializing special CPU registers to record hardware related events and read them. Those registers are also called Model Specific Registers (MSR), with one purpose of them being for the ease of debugging. They do, however, not only collect metrics for a chosen process, but instead every event on the monitored cores. So other processes, the operating system, etc. affect these measurements.

Performance monitoring itself is a very complex and daunting topic, since it requires a lot of knowledge about the used hardware, the operating system, the algorithm and in our case about the OpenBLAS implementations. The MSR differ not only between manufacturing companies, but also between CPU generations.

7.1. LIKWID

For performance monitoring the choice fell towards the open source tool LIKWID¹. It was easily integrable into the developed tool. The integration was done on an Intel Skylake CPU (Intel i3-6006u), which will be important further on. Other tools, that could have been used, are the open source tool perf or Intel's VTune, which might require a paid license for this specific usage.

Since accessing MSR has to be done on Kernel level, which is a possible security vulnerability, LIKWID comes with different access modes for the MSR. The used access mode is `accessdaemon`. On the Intel Skylake only the mode `perf_event` worked, if setting `perf_event_paranoid` to 0. Please refer to the documentation² for the meaning of the access modes and their pros/cons

LIKWID uses so-called performance groups, which are sets of events and metrics, that are to be measured. It is also possible to manually choose the events and metrics. The performance monitoring of a process can be either directly started using `likwid-perfctr` or within a process. Only one performance group can be selected at a time. It is possible to create custom performance groups and try to measure more events, with the number of available MSR as a limiting factor.

Since various architectures have different event sets and/or MSR, a new performance group is defined for each of them. For example the performance group `MEM.txt` for the Skylake

¹The used LIKWID package can be found in [13]

²<https://github.com/RRZE-HPC/likwid>

architecture collects metrics like bandwidth and loaded data volume of the RAM. On the other hand, the Zen3 architecture has only 4 registers for the 8 DRAM channels available. For this reason two performance groups MEM1.txt and MEM2.txt are defined, to take measurements for the whole CPU.

LIKWID has interfaces for the programming languages C/C++, FORTRAN, Java, Julia and Python. Since pyMOR and the developed tool are written in Python, the LIKWID Python interface called pylikwid was used and integrated into the tool. It might not be maintained anymore³, however it is just a wrapper for the C function calls, converting from Python objects to C structs and back. As long, as the LIKWID interface stays consistent, the Python interface should be usable.

However, pylikwid has in my opinion many issues. There are a lot of inconsistencies when it comes to function names and the input/output parameters compared to the C API. There is also no documentation other than the python source code pylikwid.c⁴. Combining it with the C source code e.g. perfmon.c and perfgroup.c⁵ and the C API⁶ it is possible to build up some understanding.

It seemed like a better choice to avoid the LIKWID Marker API and instead just initialize and finalize LIKWID for every run, since it was easier to set up. During benchmarking, however, the process got killed because the limit of open file descriptors was reached. This might be caused by either the way LIKWID was used or while setting the stdout and stderr to a file for every run in order to keep the terminal clean from logging messages. The measurements could be affected by this. The maximum number of descriptors for the user was increased from the default value of 1024 to 10000 using `ulimit -n 10000`, in order to continue.

Another issue I faced was about how LIKWID evaluates the metrics. As an example, lets look at the performance group L2CACHE.txt⁷ for Intel Skylake⁸ (cf. Listing 7.1). The metric 'L2 Miss Ratio' on line 17 is evaluated by the formula $\frac{PMC1}{PMC0}$ for every CPU core. On the used NUMA node there are a total of 128 (hyperthreading) CPU cores, resulting in 128 results for the 'L2 Miss Ratio'. However, a single value describing the miss ratio for a process is easier to compare. Just applying a reduce function onto all values creates wrong results. To mitigate this one can sum up all the PMC0 and PMC1 events and reevaluate the function $\frac{PMC1}{PMC0}$, with those two sums. The 'L2 Miss Ratio' and other metrics, like CPI, L2 Miss Rate, *bandwidth* and *data volume*, are evaluated like this. It is implemented into the tool using SymPy⁹. Instead of hardcoding the function manually, the corresponding LIKWID performance group file is analyzed instead.

Additionally, to the metrics defined in lines 25-32 in Listing 7.1, the metric 'cores average' was added. It is defined by the runtime of all monitored cores¹⁰ divided by the runtime of the process. The total runtime and process runtime is averaged by the performance group runs L2, L2CACHE, BRANCH, MEM1 and MEM2. All algorithms have some sequential code part. Moreover, utilizing all available cores at all times might not be the most efficient, since

³As of August 14, 2024 the last commit to the GitHub repository was done over 2 years ago

⁴<https://github.com/RRZE-HPC/pylikwid>

⁵<https://github.com/RRZE-HPC/likwid>

⁶https://rrze-hpc.github.io/likwid/Doxygen/group__PerfMon.html

⁷<https://github.com/RRZE-HPC/likwid/blob/v5.3/groups/skylake/L2CACHE.txt>

⁸The Zen3 performance group defines more events to evaluate the metrics, which makes unsuitable for the explanation.

⁹For more information about SymPy, see [19]

¹⁰It is referred to as 'runtime unhaltd' in LIKWID.

```

1 SHORT L2 cache miss rate/ratio
2
3 EVENTSET
4 FIXC0 INSTR_RETIRED_ANY
5 FIXC1 CPU_CLK_UNHALTED_CORE
6 FIXC2 CPU_CLK_UNHALTED_REF
7 PMC0 L2_TRANS_ALL_REQUESTS
8 PMC1 L2_RQSTS_MISS
9
10 METRICS
11 Runtime (RDTSC) [s] time
12 Runtime unhaltd [s] FIXC1*inverseClock
13 Clock [MHz] 1.E-06*(FIXC1/FIXC2)/inverseClock
14 CPI FIXC1/FIXC0
15 L2 request rate PMC0/FIXC0
16 L2 miss rate PMC1/FIXC0
17 L2 miss ratio PMC1/PMC0
18
19 LONG
20 Formulas:
21 L2 request rate = L2_TRANS_ALL_REQUESTS/INSTR_RETIRED_ANY
22 L2 miss rate = L2_RQSTS_MISS/INSTR_RETIRED_ANY
23 L2 miss ratio = L2_RQSTS_MISS/L2_TRANS_ALL_REQUESTS
24 -
25 This group measures the locality of your data accesses with regard to the
26 L2 cache. L2 request rate tells you how data intensive your code is
27 or how many data accesses you have on average per instruction.
28 The L2 miss rate gives a measure how often it was necessary to get
29 cache lines from memory. And finally L2 miss ratio tells you how many of your
30 memory references required a cache line to be loaded from a higher level.
31 While the data cache miss rate might be given by your algorithm you should
32 try to get data cache miss ratio as low as possible by increasing your cache reuse.

```

Listing 7.1: LIKWID performance group L2CACHE.txt for Intel Skylake architecture

synchronizing can have a great overhead. Additionally, all parallel code parts are handled by NumPy and the underlying OpenBLAS, with both having some heuristics, when to use how many threads.

As it was visible in Section 5.3, the L3 cache is especially interesting. However, as of August 14, 2024 the L3CACHE.txt group is still an open issue¹¹ for the Zen3 architecture in LIKWID. Moreover, I overlooked the CACHE.txt for Zen3 architecture, since it does not exist for Skylake. This performance group measures L1 cache Miss Ratio and Rate. Therefore, only the L2 CACHE was measured.

7.2. Over Matrix Condition Number

In Figure 7.1 one can see, that all metrics are consistent over the matrix condition number, with one exception. PGS V has for $\kappa_2(A) \approx 1$ a cores average of over 150 even though only 128 cores are available on the NUMA node. It might be a LIKWID problem, how I evaluated the metric or a failed process pinning. Moreover, the L2 Miss Rate and Ratio, and the CPI are increased. The data points should be considered as invalid.

Most variants utilize on average between 70-90 cores. SCQR has an average of around 50. Those values seem good, but an average of even up to 90 cores indicates, that the sequential code part is around 30%, in case OpenBLAS utilizes all cores in the parallel code part. This

¹¹<https://github.com/RRZE-HPC/likwid/issues/623>

can best be seen for PGS. Since it contains a lot of vector-vector operations with vectors of length 10^4 , OpenBLAS might have decided to use fewer cores. PGS has a cores average of 1.48. It barely fully utilizes the hardware, which is most definitely due to the limits of the algorithm itself, causing it to perform so poorly.

The other metrics will be discussed in the following section.

7.3. Over Matrix Size-Ratio

Since the plots in Figure 7.2 are full of possible observations only a few selected key observations will be mentioned.

In particular the L2 Miss Ratio seems off, since it is in many instances e.g. over 50%. L3 cache data would complement this observation and give more insight.

Continuing with PGS, one can see the same behavior as for the varying matrix condition number. For high size-ratios it might utilize a few more cores, but even for the single vector case it is on average only 12 cores. PGS V on the other hand utilizes for $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \approx 2$ up to 107.7 cores on average. Nevertheless, it is still highly inefficient, because of the high runtime. It is interesting to see OpenBLAS's behavior for the number of threads it uses for both PGS variants. Testing out different BLAS implementations might reveal more. Another reason both of them are so slow might be, that they have to load large amounts of data volume, which can be seen in Appendix C.

The other Gram-Schmidt variant CGS IRO LS behaves differently. It uses on average 78 cores (average over the cores average). Its L2 Miss Rate and Ratio increase especially for lower matrix size-ratios, while at the same time it decreases for the PGS variants. The CPI starts to increase drastically for $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \leq 4$ compared to the other variants. This is all connected to the data volume in Appendix C.

For $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \leq 4$, the metrics of both Householder variants start to behave differently. The runtime, CPI and Miss Rate increases with the last one having a visible spike. It is most likely related to the internally used block sizes. For lower ratios $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \leq 4$ the matrix can probably be divided in even better block sizes, resulting in low Miss Rate, Ratio and CPI. SciPy uses on average 7.8 cores more compared to NumPy and explains the lower runtime. Interestingly, one can see depending on the size-ratio a rip-saw looking usage of the cores average, because of the heuristics for the block sizes.

Shifted Choleksy QR also heavily relies on BLAS Level 3 and LAPACK's blocked Cholesky decomposition. It also utilizes a blocked triangular inverse for $Q = AR^{-1}$. Similar to NumPy and SciPy the number of threads changes around $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \approx 4$. In this case however it increases to the same values compared to CGS IRO LS. This is accompanied by small spikes in Miss Rate and Ratio.

The Gram-Schmidt based variants are clearly outperformed by the implementations utilizing BLAS Level 3 or LAPACK subroutines. PGS V might utilize the hardware a lot, but it doesn't do it efficiently. CGS IRO LS might be slightly faster compared to SCQR and NumPy for $\log_{10}(\frac{m}{n}) \geq 4$, but only while using double the amount of cores. The different block techniques used in the Householder variants and in Shifted Choleksy QR allow for more efficiency.

Figure 7.1.: LIKWID performance monitoring plots. Comparison between QR variants. Over matrix condition number plot for $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ with $n = 10^4$ generated with seed 0 with 1 iteration each.

Figure 7.2.: LIKWID performance monitoring plots. Comparison between QR variants. Over matrix size-ratio plot for $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$ generated with seed 0 with 1 iteration each.

Chapter 8.

Summary, Conclusions and Future Plans

Extensive benchmarking was shown in Chapters 5 to 7. The developed tool from Section 4.3 is still flawed, but made the process of acquiring the results much easier.

Shifted Choleksy QR is a stable algorithm, if the shift is recalculated in every iteration. Too small shifts have to be handled. One option is to enforce a minimum limit of machine epsilon. SCQR is unstable, if the shift is too large. This can be seen for $\epsilon = 1$.

If the Gramian $X = A^T A$ is too large to fit into the L2, and especially L3 caches, the norm calculation takes up more runtime. This can be mitigated by use of symmetric eigenvalue solvers. In particular `eigsh` with a relative tolerance between 10^{-1} and 10^{-4} seems to work great. Using higher tolerances does not work well. A slower alternative would be `eigh`. `fro_u` works well, but should probably be avoided as long as no proof with the correct coefficients gets published.

An interesting question that emerged is, if the first norm calculation is enough to predict at least to some degree the norms of further iterations. Being able to skip shift calculations would further improve the performance of SCQR.

Using a non-euclidian inner product is an open problem for the pyMOR implementation, since the current eigenvalue solver does not utilize the matrix symmetry, which causes high runtimes. Instead, a symmetric eigenvalue solver could be implemented in pyMOR, or a different norm be used.

As observed, both Householder variants from NumPy and SciPy are superb in runtime, efficiency and precision compared to the developed pyMOR variants. In particular the subspace angle is still an issue. The Repeated Modified Gram-Schmidt implemented in pyMOR is precise (without the mentioned tolerance) at the cost of high runtimes. PGS V might utilize the hardware more, but without a clear benefit. However, Shifted Choleksy QR with recalculated shift and CGS IRO LS proved to be reliable alternatives for pyMOR. Each of them has their own use case. SCQR is overall fast and stable. In theory, it is able to handle QR decomposition on distributed systems. Once the Gramian is too large to fit especially into the L3 cache, the runtime increases drastically, which can be mitigated by use of eigenvalue solvers for symmetric matrices.

CGS IRO LS is faster, if only a few columns have to be orthogonalized or orthogonalized against an orthonormal basis. It strongly depends on the number of columns, which would require more extensive research in order to define precise heuristics. It is also unstable for $\kappa_2(A) > 10^{15}$.

The performance monitoring in Chapter 7 gave slight insight into, what impacts the runtime of an algorithm. It can be used to identify and optimize problematic inputs.

I already started testing the performance of QR variants in algorithms, like the pyMOR thermal block demo. In the demo a non-Euclidean inner product is used for the QR decompositions.

CGS IRO LS is the only algorithm, that was faster than PGS. SCQR is too slow, and all other variants cause exceptions or results with high errors.

Furthermore, it would be necessary to test the QR implementations with different backends, like FEniCS, and on MPI distributed systems, in order to quantify performance in all scenarios.

Another test, that has to be done is benchmarking using different test matrices, especially rank deficient matrices. The varying matrix size-ratio did not give as many insights as hoped for. Rerunning tests with a limited amount of n and with varying m should give clearer insights for MOR relevant matrices.

Since the setup in the created tool already exists, adding and testing other promising QR implementations can be done easily. In particular Block-QR variants are of interest.

Bibliography

- [1] Advanced Micro Devices, Inc. (2023). *Revision Guide for AMD Family 19h Models 00h-0Fh Processors*. Version 1.08. <https://www.amd.com/content/dam/amd/en/documents/processor-tech-docs/revision-guides/56683.pdf>. (Cit. on p. 59)
- [2] Advanced Micro Devices, Inc. (2024). *AMD64 Architecture Programmer's Manual Volume 2: System Programming*. Version 3.42. <https://www.amd.com/content/dam/amd/en/documents/processor-tech-docs/programmer-references/24593.pdf>. (Cit. on p. 59)
- [3] Bartz-Beielstein, T., Doerr, C., van den Berg, D., Bossek, J., Chandrasekaran, S., Eftimov, T., Fischbach, A., Kerschke, P., Cava, W. L., Lopez-Ibanez, M., Malan, K. M., Moore, J. H., Naujoks, B., Orzechowski, P., Volz, V., Wagner, M., & Weise, T. (2020). Benchmarking in optimization: Best practice and open issues. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2007.03488>. (Cit. on p. 19)
- [4] Beyer, D., Löwe, S., & Wendler, P. (2019). Reliable benchmarking: Requirements and solutions. *International Journal on Software Tools for Technology Transfer*, 21(1), 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10009-017-0469-y> (cit. on pp. 19, 20)
- [5] Bindhak, M. (2024a). pyMOR QR decomposition and development of heuristics - code. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13304289>. (Cit. on pp. 15, 16, 42)
- [6] Bindhak, M. (2024b). pyMOR QR decomposition and development of heuristics - data. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13268682>. (Cit. on p. 15)
- [7] Carson, E., Lund, K., & Rozložník, M. (2021). The Stability of Block Variants of Classical Gram–Schmidt. *SIAM Journal on Matrix Analysis and Applications*, 42(3), 1365–1380. <https://doi.org/10.1137/21M1394424> (cit. on pp. 1, 8, 10, 15)
- [8] Carson, E., Lund, K., Rozložník, M., & Thomas, S. (2022). Block Gram-Schmidt algorithms and their stability properties. *Linear Algebra and its Applications*, 638, 150–195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.laa.2021.12.017> (cit. on p. 1)
- [9] Fritze, R., Rave, S., Schindler, F., Mlinarić, P., Balicki, L., & Kleikamp, H. (2023). *pyMOR* (Version 2023.1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8122546>. (Cit. on p. 16)
- [10] Fukaya, T., Kannan, R., Nakatsukasa, Y., Yamamoto, Y., & Yanagisawa, Y. (2020). Shifted Cholesky QR for Computing the QR Factorization of Ill-Conditioned Matrices. *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing*, 42(1), A477–A503. <https://doi.org/10.1137/18M1218212> (cit. on pp. 1, 14, 24, 38)
- [11] Georg-Johann. (2010). Illustration of the singular value decomposition $U\Sigma V^*$ of a real 2×2 matrix M . <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=11342212>. (Cit. on p. 4)
- [12] Golub, G. H., & Van Loan, C. F. (2013). *Matrix Computations - 4th Edition* (4th edition). Johns Hopkins University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1137/1.9781421407944>. (Cit. on pp. 2–7, 10, 12, 14, 30)
- [13] Gruber, T., Eitzinger, J., Hager, G., & Wellein, G. (2023). *LIKWID* (Version v5.3.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10105559>. (Cit. on p. 49)
- [14] Hoyer, S., & Hamman, J. (2017). Xarray: N-D labeled arrays and datasets in Python. *Journal of Open Research Software*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.5334/jors.148> (cit. on p. 18)
- [15] Hoyer, S., Roos, M., Joseph, H., Magin, J., Cherian, D., Fitzgerald, C., Hauser, M., Fujii, K., Maussion, F., Imperiale, G., Clark, S., Kleeman, A., Nicholas, T., Kluyver, T., Westling, J., Munroe, J., Amici, A., Barghini, A., Banihirwe, A., ... Wolfram, P. J. (2024). *Xarray* (Version v2024.05.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183201>. (Cit. on p. 18)

- [16] Knyazev, A. V., & Argentati, M. E. (2002). Principal Angles between Subspaces in an A-Based Scalar Product: Algorithms and Perturbation Estimates. *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing*, 23(6), 2008–2040. <https://doi.org/10.1137/S1064827500377332> (cit. on p. 9)
- [17] Lehoucq, R. B., Sorensen, D. C., & Yang, C. (1998). *ARPACK Users' Guide*. Society for Industrial; Applied Mathematics. <https://doi.org/10.1137/1.9780898719628>. (Cit. on p. 30)
- [18] Lund, K., Oktay, E., Carson, E. C., & Ma, Y. (2024). BlockStab. <https://github.com/katlund/BlockStab/tree/v2.2024-beta>. (Cit. on pp. 1, 10)
- [19] Meurer, A., Smith, C. P., Paprocki, M., Čertík, O., Kirpichev, S. B., Rocklin, M., Kumar, A., Ivanov, S., Moore, J. K., Singh, S., Rathnayake, T., Vig, S., Granger, B. E., Muller, R. P., Bonazzi, F., Gupta, H., Vats, S., Johansson, F., Pedregosa, F., ... Scopatz, A. (2017). Sympy: Symbolic computing in python. *PeerJ Computer Science*, 3, e103. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.103> (cit. on p. 50)
- [20] Milk, R., Rave, S., & Schindler, F. (2016). pyMOR – Generic Algorithms and Interfaces for Model Order Reduction. *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing*, 38(5), S194–S216. <https://doi.org/10.1137/15M1026614> (cit. on p. 1)
- [21] Oktay, E. (2024). *Ph.d. thesis* (Doctoral dissertation). Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Charles University, Prague. (Cit. on p. 1).
- [22] Oktay, E., & Carson, E. (2023). Using mixed precision in low-synchronization reorthogonalized block classical gram-schmidt. *PAMM*, 23(1), e202200060. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pamm.202200060> (cit. on p. 1)
- [23] pyenv developer's. (2024). pyenv. <https://github.com/pyenv>. (Cit. on p. 16)
- [24] Richter, T., & Wick, T. (2017). *Einführung in die Numerische Mathematik* (1st edition). Springer Spektrum Berlin, Heidelberg. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-54178-4>. (Cit. on pp. 2, 7, 14)
- [25] Smoktunowicz, A., Barlow, J. L., & Langou, J. (2006). A note on the error analysis of classical gram-schmidt. *Numerische Mathematik*, 105(2), 299–313. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00211-006-0042-1> (cit. on p. 12)
- [26] Świrydowicz, K., Langou, J., Ananthan, S., Yang, U., & Thomas, S. (2021). Low synchronization Gram-Schmidt and generalized minimal residual algorithms. *Numerical Linear Algebra with Applications*, 28(2), e2343. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nla.2343> (cit. on p. 11)
- [27] Wikipedia contributors. (2024a). Ieee 754 – Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia [[Online; accessed 8-August-2024]]. https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=IEEE_754&oldid=1237732264. (Cit. on p. 7)
- [28] Wikipedia contributors. (2024b). Machine epsilon – Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia [[Online; accessed 8-August-2024]]. https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Machine_epsilon&oldid=1225237390. (Cit. on p. 7)

Appendix A.

System Specifications

```
1  RELEASE INFO
2      Description:   Ubuntu 20.04.6 LTS
3      Release:      20.04
4      Codename:     focal
5
6  KERNEL INFO
7      operating system: GNU/Linux
8      kernel name:  Linux
9      kernel release: 5.15.0-69-generic
10     kernel version: #76~20.04.1-Ubuntu SMP Mon Mar 20 15:54:19 UTC 2023
11     platform type: ' x86_64 (64Bit)
12
13  VENDOR INFO
14     Dell PowerEdgeR7525 Rack Server
15
16  PROCESSOR INFO
17     CPU type: 2x AMD EPYC 7763 64-Core Processor @ 2.84 GHz
18     CPU family: 25 (19h)
19     Model: 1 (01h)
20     number of physical CPUs: 2
21     number NUMA nodes: 2
22     number of cores (physical): 128
23     number of cores (virtual): 256
24
25  CACHE INFO
26     cache level / shared by number of physical cores / size
27     L3 / 8 / 32MB
28     L2 / 1 / 512KB
29     L1I / 1 / 32KB
30     L1D / 1 / 32KB
31
32  MEMORY INFO
33     RAM installed: 1 TB
34     SWAP installed: 0 GB
35
36  Version of the GNU Compiler Collection
37     gcc\g++\gfortran (Ubuntu 9.4.0-1ubuntu1~20.04.2) 9.4.0
38
39  Version of the GNU C Library
40     libc: 2.31
41
42  default BLAS shared object version
43     openblas 0.3.8+ds-1ubuntu0.20.04.1
44
45  default LAPACK shared object version
46     openblas 0.3.8+ds-1ubuntu0.20.04.1
47
48  LIKWID version
49     5.3.0
50
51  PYTHON INFO
52     python      3.8.10
53     pymor       # see reference
54     numpy       1.24.4
55     scipy       1.10.1
56     pylikwid    0.4.2
```

Listing A.1: Overview of the system specifications and used software versions. More information about the CPU and performance monitoring events can be found in [1, 2].

Figure A.1.: System topology generated using lstopo.

Appendix B.

Matrix size-ratio table

$\approx \log_{10}\left(\frac{m}{n}\right)$	$\approx \frac{m}{n}$	m	n	Gramian size in MB
8.0000	100 000 000.00	100000000	1	0.000
7.3979	25 000 000.00	50000000	2	0.000
6.7959	6 250 000.00	25000000	4	0.000
6.6021	4 000 000.00	20000000	5	0.000
6.1938	1 562 500.00	12500000	8	0.001
6.0000	1 000 000.00	10000000	10	0.001
5.5918	390 625.00	6250000	16	0.002
5.3979	250 000.00	5000000	20	0.003
5.2041	160 000.00	4000000	25	0.005
4.9897	97 656.25	3125000	32	0.008
4.7959	62 500.00	2500000	40	0.013
4.6021	40 000.00	2000000	50	0.020
4.3876	24 414.06	1562500	64	0.033
4.1938	15 625.00	1250000	80	0.051
4.0000	10 000.00	1000000	100	0.080
3.8062	6400.00	800000	125	0.125
3.7856	6103.52	781250	128	0.131
3.5918	3906.25	625000	160	0.205
3.3979	2500.00	500000	200	0.320
3.2041	1600.00	400000	250	0.500
3.1835	1525.88	390625	256	0.524
2.9897	976.56	312500	320	0.819
2.7959	625.00	250000	400	1.280
2.6021	400.00	200000	500	2.000
2.4082	256.00	160000	625	3.125
2.3876	244.14	156250	640	3.277
2.1938	156.25	125000	800	5.120
2.0000	100.00	100000	1000	8.000
1.8062	64.00	80000	1250	12.500
1.7856	61.04	78125	1280	13.107
1.5918	39.06	62500	1600	20.480
1.3979	25.00	50000	2000	32.000
1.2041	16.00	40000	2500	50.000
1.0103	10.24	32000	3125	78.125
0.9897	9.77	31250	3200	81.920
0.7959	6.25	25000	4000	128.000
0.6021	4.00	20000	5000	200.000
0.4082	2.56	16000	6250	312.500
0.3876	2.44	15625	6400	327.680
0.1938	1.56	12500	8000	512.000
0.0000	1.00	10000	10000	800.000

Table B.1.: Matrix sizes $((m, n)$ pairs) and the resulting size-ratios $\left(\frac{m}{n}\right)$ used in this thesis.
 $m, n \in \mathbb{N}_{>0}$ with $m \geq n$ and $m \cdot n = 10^8$
For SCQR added the size of Gramian in MB $(8 \cdot n^2)$.

Appendix C.

Additional Performance Monitoring Plots

Appendix C contains 2 additional graphics related to Chapter 7. Figure C.1 and Figure C.2 show the loaded/stored data volume and average bandwidth of the RAM and prefetcher. They are measured using the LIKWID performance groups L2.txt, MEM1.txt and MEM2.txt. The data volume and bandwidth results from MEM1.txt and MEM2.txt are added together.

Figure C.1.: LIKWID performance monitoring plots. Comparison between QR variants. Over matrix condition number plot for $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ with $n = 10^4$ generated with seed 0 with 2 iterations each.

Figure C.2.: LIKWID performance monitoring plots. Comparison between QR variants. Over matrix size-ratio plot for $\kappa_2(A) \approx 10^{20}$ generated with seed 0 with 2 iterations each.